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NERSC TECHNICAL REPORT NO. 183

OPERALT

OPERATIONAL ALTIMETRY FOR THE OFFSHORE INDUSTRY

EUROPEAN COMMISSION ENVIRONMENT AND CLIMATE PROGRAMME 1994 - 1998

THEME 3: SPACE TECHNIQUES APPLIED TO ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND RESEARCH

AREA 3.3.3 CENTRE FOR EARTH OBSERVATION APPLICATION SUPPORT

FINAL REPORT

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April 2000

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<p>TITLE OPERALT Development of a pre-operational ocean current measurement system using altimetry</p>	<p>REPORT IDENTIFICATION OPERALT Final Report</p>
<p>CLIENT CEC - DGXII Environmental and Climate Programme</p>	<p>CONTRACT ENV4-CT98-0739</p>
<p>CLIENT REFERENCE Tiziano Businaro</p>	<p>AVAILABILITY Open</p>
<p>INVESTIGATORS Ola M. Johannesen (coordinator), S. Sandven, J. A. Johannessen, P. Samuel, V. Haugen, P-Y. LeTraon, C. Boone, H. J. Sætre and T. Hamre</p>	<p>AUTHORISATION Bergen: 28 April 2000 DIRECTOR Ola M. Johannessen</p>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Objectives

The objective of the OPERALT project was to develop a pre-operational altimeter data analysis and archival system for ocean currents, and to assess the benefits and cost-effectiveness of the ocean current information provided by such EO data for applications by a major customer group: the offshore oil industry.

Sea level measurements by satellite radar altimeters (RA) represent a relatively low-cost data which can be used for global mapping for ocean currents. Recent improvements in orbit determinations and geoid modeling, and the availability of overlapping coverage from two satellites ERS and Topex/Poseidon have been exploited in this project in order to estimate regional currents more accurately which is required by oil companies producing oil from floating platforms primarily in deep offshore areas.

The specific objectives are:

- To produce an accurate high-resolution local altimetric mean sea level for the prime study area.
- To produce merged ERS-1/2 and Topex/Poseidon data sets for the study area in the period October~1992 to October~1998.
- To validate altimeter-derived current estimates against in situ measurements.
- To develop appropriate altimeter data products based on feedback from offshore oil industry.
- To assess the benefits and cost-effectiveness of Near Real Time (NRT) as well as offline altimeter data products during a pre-operational implementation phase.

Main tasks and achievements

The offshore industry 's requirements for oceanographical data

As oil exploration and production activities move from the continental shelf to deeper waters, information on the ocean current field becomes increasingly important. Satellite altimetry can provide important input in this context, and this project is an attempt at maximising the benefits of altimeter data for offshore oil exploration, production and support activities.

The offshore petroleum exploration is moving from the Norwegian Continental Shelf (NCS) at water depths of 200 – 400 m to the continental slope areas with depths from 500 to more than 2000 m. The offshore industry in Norway has instituted a joint meteorological and oceanographic (Metocean) project within the Norwegian Deepwater Programme in connection with opening of new licenses in deep waters off Mid-Norway. The meteorological and oceanographic conditions of these areas are generally more extreme than at the NCS

because of the greater exposure to the Atlantic Ocean and the Norwegian Sea. One of the aims of the Metocean project is to obtain knowledge about current conditions required for design and operation of floating structures. Use of SAR data and satellite altimeter data from the OPERALT project was included in the observation programme in the Metocean project.

The study region west of Mid-Norway has complicated bathymetry, combined with strong ocean currents and fronts between Norwegian Atlantic Current and the Norwegian Coastal Current. Therefore the ocean currents in the area have high mesoscale variability, with generation of meanders and eddies representing the maximum current velocities which is a key factor for design and operation of floating offshore platforms. Hence, regular monitoring over an extended period of time is necessary to obtain reliable statistics on the current regime, including mesoscale eddy activity. This area is also subject to severe wave conditions, exposed to propagation of long-period waves from the North Atlantic, interacting with the ocean currents, creating confused seas with wave heights higher than can be attributed to ambient weather conditions.

Satellite remote sensing techniques for observation of meteorological and oceanographical phenomena have developed rapidly in the last 10 years, especially microwave methods such as radar altimetry and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imaging of ocean surface processes. For many years satellite data were limited to optical and infrared sensors which could mainly be used to observe clouds and surface temperature as part of the global meteorological observations system. With the development of microwave radar techniques it is now possible to observe and quantify several processes and phenomena at the sea surface such as waves, winds, fronts, eddies, currents, slicks and atmospheric boundary layer processes.

The main advantage of satellite data is the capability of synoptic observations over large areas. When these synoptic observations are coordinated with *in situ* wind, wave and current measurements optimal data sets can be established to characterize meteorological and oceanographical conditions over large ocean areas. Satellite data will not replace use of traditional measurements from current moorings, but serve as an important supplement and contribute to more cost-effective use of expensive moorings. The oil and gas industry has therefore started to use satellite data to study and monitor met-ocean conditions in offshore areas. In OPERALT the possibility to use altimeter data to provide current parameters required by the offshore industry has been demonstrated.

Analysis of TOPEX/Poseidon and ERS altimeter data

The first stage in the analysis of altimeter data is to estimate the mean, time-invariant sea surface elevation from several satellite altimeters: GEOSAT Exact Repeat Mission, Topex/Poseidon and ERS-1/2. Maps of mean sea surface elevation reflects the horizontal variation of the geoid due to sea mounts and trenches. The mean levels were calculated for each satellite separately due to the different temporal and spatial sampling of the satellite systems. In the further analysis, the mean sea surface elevation was subtracted from the

altimetric heights from each orbit to derive the sea level anomaly (SLA). In this process the effect of the geoid was removed. A number of other effects with impact on the range measurements also had to be removed from the SLA data before ocean current information could be derived. These included corrections due to dry/wet troposphere, inverse barometric pressure, ionospheric effects, sea state bias, tidal correction and others.

The processing of the altimeter data consisted of the following steps:

- Remove orbit error: Global cross over minimisation using the more accurate T/P altimeter data as the reference to reduce ERS-1/2 orbit error.
- Creation of SLA: Relative to a 3 year mean profile, consistent for T/P and ERS.
- Filtering of SLA: Using a loess filter to remove high frequency signal over 63 km for along track calculation of geostrophic velocities, over 35 kilometres to smooth the data before sampling the mapping procedure.
- Sampling of SLA: every other data point (every 14 km) from the SLA profiles filtered at 35 km to create super-observations.
- Mapping of SLA (MSLA): sub-optimal space and time objective analysis to map the super-observations on to a grid (0.2 degrees in longitude, 0.1 in latitude) using appropriate altimetric data error statistics (10% T/P, 15% ERS) and appropriate correlation scales (15 days - 90 km). Long wavelength errors are also removed (residual orbit error, tide and inverse barometer errors). Mapping errors are also estimated as a results of the method used for the mapping.

The data products derived from altimeter data were the following:

- Along track Sea Surface Height Anomalies (SLA)
- SLA derived geostrophic velocities anomalies (GVELA) perpendicular to the track.
- Time series of profiles of SLA and GVELA from the same orbit
- Time series of SLA and GVELA data from the same location
- Mapped Sea Surface Height Anomalies (MSLA) and associated mapping errors (in percentage of the signal variance). Mapping is performed over 20 days of data (T_0-20 to T_0), on to a precise date: T_0-10 days for HH (therefore the map is centered), and T_0-5 days for NRT (therefore the map is de-centered, consequently to a trade-off between accuracy and time delay).
- Mapped geostrophic velocities anomalies (MGVELA), calculated from MSLA using a finite difference scheme. These gridded vectors (zonal u_g' and meridional v_g') can be overlaid on to the corresponding MSLA field and SAR imagery showing fronts and eddies.
- Sea wave height in NRT (as an example)
- Wind speed in NRT (as an example)
- Maps of the distribution of Eddy Kinetic Energy ($EKE=1/2(\langle u_g'^2 \rangle + \langle v_g'^2 \rangle)$)
- Maps of the distribution of the Reynolds Stresses ($\langle u_g' u_g' \rangle$, $\langle v_g' v_g' \rangle$, $\langle u_g' v_g' \rangle$)

Validation against in situ observations

A three-year time series of cross-track current anomalies from Topex/Poseidon Track no. 42 was compared with current measurements from an Aanderaa mooring array located about 30 km from the altimeter track. The Aanderaa data were processed and resampled to be compatible with the altimeter data. The correlation between the two data types was up to 0.65 which is a reasonable good match between two current measurement series obtained 30 km apart from each other. Another validation method was to compare instantaneous cross-track velocity profiles with flow pattern in SAR imagery. The SAR images do not provide quantitative estimates of current speed, but they indicate flow direction and the presence of fronts and eddies. In a few cases where SAR and altimeter data were compared, there was good agreement between the altimeter-derived current and the SAR flow pattern.

The overall assessment of the altimeter products are shown in the following table:

Products	Advantages	Limitations
Eddy Kinetic Energy maps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show areas of high eddy activity • Provide monthly, seasonal and interannual variability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • time and space resolution is not good enough to resolve the whole eddy spectrum
Reynold Stress maps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shows directionality of the current variability • similar statistics as for EKE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • similar to EKE
Time series of Sea Level Anomalies in fixed locations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful for spectral analysis, comparison with current, temperature, etc. records • Can correlate time series in different locations to study signal propagation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • temporal resolution (10 days) is insufficient to resolve many mesoscale signals
Time series of cross-track velocity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtain geostrophic current normal to the track, comparison with sections of in situ measurements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the altimeter track must be normal to the main current
Velocity anomaly maps averaged over 10 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shows velocity field after removal of the time-invariant field • Can supplement with instantaneous cross-track velocities and SAR imagery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ten day is too long averaging time • interpretation of the velocity can be difficult

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

- Use of satellite altimeter data to derive ocean current information has been developed to a stage where the offshore industry has started to use the altimeter techniques together with traditional oceanographical methods in exploration of deepwater areas. The global coverage of altimeter data offers unique opportunity to estimate current parameters anywhere in the world where the oil and gas industry plans offshore operations.
- The offshore industry is a key market for oceanographical data, and the requirements from this industry drive much of the development of new marine observation and monitoring methods. In OPERALT the study area off Mid Norway was selected because of the ongoing offshore operations in this region require the best available information on currents. Accurate current data are essential both for design and operation of floating, anchored constructions. The study area was also selected because both ERS and Topex/Poseidon altimeter cover the region since 1992.
- In order to extract current information from altimeter data, sea level anomaly (SLA) from Topex/Poseidon and ERS have been analyzed for the study area off west Norway. Due to the user requirements, two types of analyses have been done:
 - HH (homogeneous historical) data over 6 years (1992 – 1999) which provide useful statistical estimates of mean and variance of SLA which provide input data to the design criteria for offshore construction
 - NRT (near real time) data delivered within a week which provide monitoring of 10 day averaged conditions which is useful for operations
- The results of the SLA analysis show good accuracy of NRT with respect to HH data, although a bias exists between the two data sets: 2 cm in square root of the variance of Mapped Sea Level Anomaly (MSLA), and 3 cm RMS of the MSLA.
- The SLA data can be used to calculate several current products such as Eddy Kinetic Energy, Reynold stresses, time series at fixed locations, time series of cross-track velocity along sections, and 10-day averaged velocity anomaly maps.
- Altimeter data provide unique information on these current parameters due to the regular coverage in space and time. The accuracy and fast delivery of NRT altimetric data can provide important information on currents which cannot be obtained by other methods

- Some of the current products have been validated against in situ current observations and SAR images. Results are encouraging, but more validation work is needed.
- Inherent limitations of existing altimeter data are due to the spatial (20 – 30 km) and temporal resolution (10 days) in the study area. This means that mesoscale variability of the currents cannot be fully resolved at high latitudes. Nevertheless, the 10-day current maps have proven to be realistic and in agreement with current structures observed in SAR imagery.
- Expected improvement of altimetric data quality and the derived current products in the next few years will be due to
 - better software for data analysis
 - improved calculation of long wavelength errors
 - improved mapping methodology of the data with better characterisation of the time and space scales of the ocean signal, and the estimation of propagation velocities.
 - ESA's higher GOCE mission (schedule for launch in 2005) will improve the determination of the marine geoid required to determine absolute topography instead of SLA
 - new altimeter satellites (Geosat Follow on, Jason-1 and ENVISAT) will secure continuous access to data
- The specific requirements from the offshore industry to future altimeter-derived current information are:
 - higher temporal resolution than 10 days to capture the mesoscale current variability, which can be obtained by clever combination and processing of data from several satellites
 - better validation of the mesoscale current fields by comparison with oceanographical time series as well as models
 - direct observation of current instead of current anomalies, which will be possible when the marine geoid is determined by GOCE to an accuracy of 1 – 2 cm over 100 km
 - good forecasting of the currents. Altimeter-derived current data together with ocean models (data assimilation) will be a powerful tool for improved ocean forecasting

1. Project management (WP 1000)

1.1 Organisation

The project is divided into five main work packages with corresponding sub-work packages which are summarised in Table 1:

Table 1. Work packages and leaders

WP no.	WP title	WP leader
WP1000	Project management	NERSC
WP1100	Management plan	NERSC
WP1200	Monitoring schedule	NERSC
WP1300	Quality assurance	NERSC
WP2000	Project definition	NERSC
WP2100	User requirements	Norske Shell
WP2200	Redefinition of project	NERSC
WP2300	Technical requirements	NERSC
WP2400	Verification plan	NERSC
WP3000	Implementation	CLS
WP3100	Mean sea surface	CLS
WP3200	Combined analysis	CLS
WP3300	Product development	NERSC
WP4000	Validation and verification	NERSC
WP4100	Validation by intercomparison	CLS
WP4200	Validation against field data	NERSC
WP4300	Validation against model data	NERSC
WP4300	Verification of results	Norske Shell
WP5000	Exploitation	NERSC
WP5100	Cost-benefit analysis	Norske Shell
WP5200	Dissemination	NERSC

1.2 Management plan

The project co-ordinator is Stein Sandven, NERSC, who is leading the project according to the management plan illustrated by the Gantt and Pert diagram and the project schedule shown in Appendix A1. The co-ordinator is communicating directly with the WP leader and scientists working in each of the WPs, using e-mail, telephone or meetings. Exchange of data have taken place between CLS and NERSC, while Norsk Shell has primarily contributed with a user requirement report and input to definition and validation of the products.

1.3 Summary of WP results and deliverables

Table 2 presents a summary of results and deliverables from each work package, while more detailed description of the work is presented in Chapters 2 to 5.

Table 2: Summary of WP results and deliverables.

Work Package	RESULTS	DELIVERABLES
WP 1000: Project Management		Management Plan and Quality Assurance Plan (Appendix A1)
WP 2000: Project Definition	Requirements specified by Norske Shell were used in the development of altimeter products	Customer requirement document Technical requirements Verification plan
WP 3100: Mean Sea Surface	Mean sea surface computed separately for the different altimeter missions	Mean sea surface estimate (progress report, annual report and final report)
WP 3200: Combined Analysis	The altimeter data used for this study comes from Topex/Poseidon, ERS-1 cersat-1, ERS-1 cersat-2 and ERS-2 cersat-2, from October 1992 to December 1998. In order to merge ERS-1/2 and T/P data, homogeneous altimetric corrections were applied to the data sets and a global crossover minimisation using T/P data as reference was carried out in order to reduce ERS-1/2 orbit error.	Along-track and gridded sea level and geostrophic velocity anomalies (progress report, annual report and final report) Data available on ftp site cd pub/oceano/OPERALT/
WP 3300: Product Development	Product list includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RMS anomalies of sea surface height, • Seasonal maps of eddy kinetic energy (EKE), • Seasonal maps of Reynolds Stress, • along-track SLA, • cross-track velocity anomalies, • distance-time plots of along track SLA and cross-track velocity anomalies, • time series of SLA and velocity anomalies at selected points, • mapped SLA and current anomaly plots, • current velocities overlaid on SAR imagery, sea wave height and wind speed. 	Examples of data products (progress report, annual report and final report).
WP 4100: Validation by intercomparison	Mean sea surfaces from ERS-2 and T/P show local inconsistencies. The accuracy of the NRT is about 2 cm RMS for the T/P and ERS-2 combined maps, and the accuracy is better for along track data.	Accuracy estimates for mean sea surface and mapped anomaly fields (final report).
WP 4200/WP4300: Validation against field & model data	Validation of T/P current anomalies against 4 current meter moorings completed using times series of about 3 years Validation against model results have been done qualitatively	Current field accuracy estimates (final report).
WP 4400: Verification	Norske Shell has performed an overall assessment of the data products	Verification of project results (final report)
WP 5100: Cost-benefit analysis	Cost-benefit analysis was replaced by a qualitative assessment by a consortium of oil companies suggesting that use of altimeter data is a useful and cost-effective supplement to traditional current measurement systems	Cost-benefit assessment (final report)
WP 5200: Dissemination	Project web site was created: (http://www.nrsc.no/Operalt). A 2-page project flier was made and distributed at conferences Results have been presented at a meeting at several conferences and workshops focusing on offshore activities. Efforts will continue to show results to potential customers.	Web site Flier (see Appendix) Papers and presentation at conferences Data available on ftp site cd pub/oceano/OPERALT/

1.4 Project monitoring and reports

There have been three official projects meetings: the Kick-off meeting at NERSC in August 1998, the first progress meeting in March 1999, and the second progress meeting at CLS in October 1999. The first progress report and the user requirements report was prepared and submitted to the project officer in Brussels in May – June 1999. An annual report was provided in December 1999. The draft Final report was delivered before the Final presentation in Brussels on 24 February 2000.

1.5 Quality assurance

The progress of the project has been overlooked by Prof. Ola M. Johannessen, the director of the Nansen Center. The quality assurance plan is shown in Appendix A1.

1.6 Personnel

The scientists who have worked on the project are:

NERSC: Dr. Paul Samuel, Vibeke J. Haugen, Stein Sandven, and Dr. Torill Hamre. Dr. Johnny A. Johannessen has been involved in the project in the last six months (September 1998 – February 2000) instead of P. Samuel who left the Nansen Center by the end of October 1999.

CLS: Dr. Pierre-Yves Le Traon, Dr. Christine Boone

Norske Shell: Hans Jørgen Sætre.

1.7 Problems encountered and change in work plan

It was originally planned to produce a precise and high-resolution mean sea surface by combining GEOSAT, ERS-1/2 and Topex/Poseidon data. However, a preliminary examination of the individual mean sea surfaces revealed significant differences in some regions of the study area. Consequently, it was decided not to merge the data into a common mean sea surface, but to use the individual mean sea surfaces for computing anomalies from the respective data sets.

Orbit error in the Topex/Poseidon data is assumed to be insignificant in the processing. However, a closer examination of the computed along-track anomalies indicates a possibility that this might not be a valid assumption in the study area.

A cost-benefit analysis could not be carried out because real data for such analysis were not available. Instead a qualitative cost-benefit assessment was carried out by Norske Shell.

2. Project definition (WP 2000)

2.1 User requirements (WP 2100)

A user requirements report was prepared describing the background and needs from the offshore industry for meteorological and oceanographical information. The results of the study are presented in the following section. The offshore oil and gas industry has a long tradition to obtain and utilise meteorological and oceanographic (metocean) data, and they are mainly used to establish design and operational criteria for field developments. The strive to improve weather and sea-state forecasts is another. Accurate data are of foremost importance because operations have to be performed in a safe and cost-effective manner. Already in the late sixties and early seventies it became clear that in the North Sea the wave and wind climatology were largely underestimated when they were produced from rather crude and inaccurate ocean atlases based on visual ship observations. This caused a need to extend ongoing measurements and establish new locations for long-term *in situ* buoy measurements. With maturity of the area, these programmes have been exchanged with a network of platform-based monitoring stations.

The backbone of metocean information is still *in situ* measurements but simulated results from numerical models and remotely sensed data are now playing an even more important role in providing data for the industry. With the development of microwave radar techniques it is now possible to observe and quantify several processes and phenomena at the sea surface such as waves, winds, fronts, eddies and current features. Some would say that to some extent satellite altimeter data have dramatically changed our way of obtaining ocean wave and wind information.

This note addresses the application of altimeter data to acquire ocean current data for the offshore industry. Sea surface anomaly or topography, from which ocean currents and sea bed shape can be deduced, is an application which is the development phase and few attempts have been done to compare altimeter data with *in situ* current measurements and results of ocean modelling (see chapter below). The full potential of the application has not yet been shown. In order to discuss possible requirements, the different stages of the offshore exploration and production (E&P) process and the need for metocean data are described. Some of the data are needed for statistical purposes and some are needed in real-time for forecast purposes.

2.1.1 Needs Developed in the Norwegian Deepwater Programme

Following the 1996 award of deepwater licenses, the offshore industry in Norway instituted a joint metocean project within the Norwegian Deepwater Programme to acquire data for the exploration and development phases in the new area. An overall and very general data acquisition programme on ocean currents was established. Because the consequence of excessively conservative criteria and procedures may be quite different for a deepwater

producing system, it was only through a full understanding of the physical environment and accurate engineering procedures that we can hope to carry out deepwater development in a safe and cost effective manner. The data acquisition system has taken advantage of extensive use of moored acoustic Doppler current profilers, 3-dimensional numerical ocean model to simulate currents and current statistics, and remote sensing data from earth orbiting satellites to study velocity anomalies and mesoscale ocean features such as fronts and eddies. Three main issues – the integrated data acquisition system, data correlation analysis and the temporal and spatial variability of the currents – have been addressed. Although the 4 – 5 year project is not completed yet, it may be concluded that a high proportion of the objectives has been obtained, and that future field developments in the Norwegian deepwater areas can base their design on a sound and viable metocean database.

2.1.2 Main Characteristics of the Exploration and Production Process

The offshore oil and gas activities are process oriented and, where appropriate, reflect the concept of the life cycle management. Five consecutive steps are defined and the meteorological and oceanographic activities are also related to the life cycle process as shown in Table 4 (next page).

2.1.3 Metocean Parameters Used by the Offshore Oil and Gas Industry

Derivation of Metocean Criteria

The complete list of metocean parameters is defined below and these parameters shown in Table 3, will be considered for any data acquisition or simulation programme. The derivation of Metocean criteria are illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2.

Table 3. Overview of the Metocean parameters

Meteorological	Oceanographic
Wind Speed /direction	Wave Height, Period & Direction
Air Temperature	Current Speed & Direction with Depth
Humidity	Tides
Precipitation	Storm Surge
Barometric Pressure	Sea Temperature
Cloud Cover	Salinity
Visibility	Ice cover

Adequate data are obtained by:

- ◆ Specific in situ measurements from buoys and platforms (fixed and floating)
- ◆ Model simulations (wind and wave hindcast, 2-D & 3-D current hindcast, tides, surges)
- ◆ Remote sensing (sea surface temperature, waves, ice cover)
- ◆ Archived data (meteorological parameters, sea temperature & salinity)

Table 4. Requirements for the exploration and production phases

Phases	General E&P and Specific Metocean Activities
Explore	<p>The exploration phase includes design and execution of surveys required to measure and record surface and subsurface attributes of a specific area. Surveys include seismic targets, shallow gas/hydrate hazard identification, site surveys (seabed/metocean), geo-technical coring, gravity and magnetic etc.</p> <p><i>The metocean survey design includes support to the exploration operations (seismic, drilling, installation, maintenance and oil spill assistance) but because of the timing and the need for sufficient time to acquire metocean data, it is important that the metocean activity in this phase includes elements that can be carried through into later phases of the process. For instance, the need for long-term data of winds, waves and currents should be established at an early stage and this is essential when exploration is performed in new deepwater areas</i></p>
Appraise	<p>The appraisal phase covers the planning and execution of all activities to quantify economic potential (technical risks and opportunities) of potential hydrocarbon discoveries, including the steps involved to select the most suitable concept for development. This process leads to the required Plan to Develop and Operate (PDO) submitted to the authorities.</p> <p><i>The main metocean investigations are completed in this phase and the results are compiled as part of the Design Basis. The metocean design and operational criteria are an important element in the PDO to justify that the selected development concept is safe to install and operate. The criteria at this stage are often preliminary, as data acquisition may still go on.</i></p>
Develop	<p>The development phase covers the construction, installation and pre-commissioning of the facilities. The detail engineering is reviewed and completed early in the process and modifications (change of design) are carried out.</p> <p><i>The metocean activities are related to finalising the Design Basis and support of offshore operations (mating, towing and heavy lifts). A metocean real-time data acquisition system is design and constructed.</i></p>
Produce	<p>The operation of the integrated production system (offshore field) is the basic element of the production phase. The field shall be operated in a safe and efficient manner over an identified period (typical 20 years in Norwegian waters).</p> <p><i>The metocean activities are concentrated to deliver real-time data and forecasts for the day-to-day operations but it is also necessary to update operational metocean statistics based on site-specific information. Many structures and parts of structures are equipped with load sensors and the structural integrity is checked continuously or periodically against the environmental forces. A revision of the metocean design criteria may also be needed during the production phase ("safety case") to document any changes from the original design values.</i></p>
Abandon	<p>The abandonment phase includes the detail planning and execution of all activities to abandon facilities and restore the site. Abandonment planning has also been carried out in earlier phases and necessary construction details implemented during the construction phase.</p> <p><i>The metocean activities are limited to support of offshore operations (heavy lifts and towing) and coastal deployment. Weather forecasting and real-time measurements are the main needs.</i></p>

Figure 1. Derivation of metocean criteria.

Figure 2. Variation in metocean criteria with application.

2.1.4 Different Applications of Remote Sensing Data in the Offshore Oil and Gas Industry

OPERATIONS IN ICE INFESTED AREAS

Ice infested areas put special requirements to operation and design of structures, and remote sensing has played an important role to improve the data basis on ice. Information on the sea ice extent is used on a routine basis along with weather forecasts. In addition, information on first year and multi-year ice, and the size of floes are of vital interest. SAR images provide useful information on these conditions where it is needed. Iceberg detection and drift is another very important topic and a lot of research work has been dedicated to the problem. RADARSAT has overcome some of the earlier problems encountered with ERS-1.

Examples: Extensive use of satellite data was utilised at the Siberian Shelf where oil and gas transport has been evaluated for many concepts (terminal at Kolguev, pipelines from Yamal). In the Sea of Okhotsk, offshore field development has been evaluated at the north-east coast of Sakhalin.

Wind and Wave Conditions

Far-reaching work is presently performed to utilise radar altimeter data, and results are positive and encouraging. For instance, spatial variations of the wave field are now extensively determined by altimeter data and applications at remote locations have proved its success. The spatial resolution is much better than grids based on numerical models and especially close to islands and shorelines are the data of better quality. However, validations against reference buoy data are strongly needed to remove systematic bias. This is because storm conditions are of utmost importance and good extreme wave, wind and ocean current data are needed. Attempts to combine corrected altimeter data and in situ measurements by filling gaps in the measured time series has so far not been successful.

Weather Forecasting

Reliable weather forecasts get increasingly more important as offshore operations become more complex and the industry moves to deeper waters and harsher environment. Assimilation of the scatterometer and altimeter data will be the main application to drive the quality of forecasts forward. It is a fact that forecasts based on assimilated ERS-1 data has proved higher skill than forecasts that do not utilise ERS-1 data. The endeavour to make use of ERS-1 wave data in nowcast systems has proved its usefulness. A challenge for ocean-wave modellers will still be to assimilate continuously the large stream of SAR wave-mode data in operational wave models in a cost-effective manner. Many National Meteorological centres run numerical wave models operationally side by side with numerical weather prediction models (UK Met. Office, KNMI in the Netherlands and DNMI in Norway).

Example: An assimilation method for spectral wave observations has been tested in the North Sea wave model over a one-year period. It is found that the assimilation improves the model estimate of the seastate up to at least 24 hours in forecast, especially under swell conditions.

OCEAN CURRENT, FRONTS AND EDDIES

The ability to process radar altimeter data with regard to sea surface height anomalies and velocity anomalies are showing promising results. Recent studies of the Norwegian Atlantic Current have shown both mesoscale variability and spatial distribution that is advantageous in understanding the current regime of the area. Ongoing work to merge data sets from two satellite missions seems to provide a better spatial and temporal data set. Another application would be studies of mesoscale ocean features such as fronts and eddies. These are imaged by a characteristic pattern of surfactants or due to associated shear or convergence zones. The impact and discovery of whirls at the Troll Field in the Norwegian Trough is a classical example.

Seismic and Facilities Planning

Satellite imagery provides a powerful visualisation tool, especially combined with terrain height data. This technique can be adopted in many key stages in the E&P lifecycle process. Geological interpretation and engineering are two of the most utilised areas.

Route Planning

Route planning is widely applied through the business and it benefits greatly from what is called Digital Elevation Models (DEM). In pipeline or seismic planning, DEM and other appropriate software will provide calculations of slope vectors, longitudinal profiles and various statistics. Although these methods are mostly used in onshore applications, they can be extended to nearshore areas in shallow water depths (landfall of pipelines, terminal/harbour construction, navigation channels, sand movement).

Examples: Landsat images were used in Egypt for the purpose of seismic planning. This was particularly important in cultivated areas where access restrictions caused logistical difficulties and high expenses if the planning was not carried out in an optimal manner. GPS control points were used to correct the images so that accurate topographical maps could be produced. These images were also used for geological interpretation in dune areas and for environmental assessment. In Pakistan, a DEM was created from SPOT Panchromatic Imagery (10 m) images. This enabled quantitative information about seismic line profiles to be calculated. A Landsat TM image was draped over the model to give information about land cover and terrain type. Profiles for specific lines can be plotted to highlight problem areas. DEM also assisted in the decision making process for a proposed pipeline in the Temir region (Kazakhstan). An initial route was chosen but a refined examination of the satellite imagery made it possible to find a better route with regard to elevation and slope. In Nigeria, it was

preferable to avoid habitation while acquiring seismic for logistical and environmental reasons. Landsat TM was merged with SPOT Pan to give a 10 m resolution. Due to the persistent cloud cover in the Delta area, experiments were carried out with high-resolution Radarsat data.

Geological Interpretation

Satellite imagery provides a relatively low cost method of gaining knowledge about potential acreage at the stage when investment is being kept at a minimum. This applies to new acreage both off- and onshore. It is especially useful in sensitive areas where political or environmental matters make other means difficult to achieve. Another important issue is that there is no restriction on areas for which satellite images can be purchased.

Natural Hydrocarbon Seepage

In offshore locations, satellite images (radar data in particular) are used to give an indication of the presence of hydrocarbon charge. The technique – although still subjective - is well proven for oil seepage and it is widely used in new acreage or 'green field' areas. In well-developed areas such as the North Sea, it is a challenge to distinguish natural seep from seeps from platforms and ship traffic. For gas, this technique is unproven and currently being researched. In onshore locations, it is not easy to detect seepage although there are some areas where it is possible. It is, however, possible to carry out preliminary geological interpretation. Surface expressions of structural variations may be identified on satellite images but not easily visible on the ground. In areas which have previously been explored, the extent of activities such as seismic and wells can be identified.

Example: In China, an old exploration area was looked upon as a new acreage and there was a need to determine the number of wells drilled. A merged image was used to provide the necessary resolution.

ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT

Satellite imagery provides a quantitative method to detect changes to the ground cover, and such base-line studies are important for documentation purposes. Oil pollution in offshore and coastal areas can be easily detected as long as it is related to platforms. Ship pollution is more difficult to detect but the satellite information can narrow down areas of particular concern for further surveillance.

Examples: In an area with many oil platforms offshore Brunei, a satellite image showed an oil spill from one of the platforms. Strong currents were carrying the oil in a north-westerly direction while the wind direction was 90 degree off the current direction. Time lapse imagery has been used in Nigeria since 1979 to indicate changes in the ground cover. Some ground truth information is needed to identify particular features.

2.2 Redefinition of project (WP 2200)

There has been no redefinition of the project

2.3 Technical requirements (WP 2300)

2.3.1 Possible Applications of Altimeter Data to Obtain Ocean Current Information

There are four basic ways of applying metocean data. These are:

- ◆ **Statistical analysis to derive extremes (design criteria).** This requires long time series of accurate measurements of good coverage or simulations because it is the tail of the distribution or the annual maximum that is required for the analysis. A vital question will always be if seasonal or annual variations have been picked up by the measurement period. Traditionally, ocean currents have been measured for periods of 2 – 12 months to cover for a winter period but for waves the data acquisition period is typically 5 years or more.
- ◆ **Statistical analysis to derive operational criteria.** The same time series as above are used but it is important that they are continuous without gaps (duration or occurrence statistics, weather windows). Simulated or measured series with infill of simulated data are mainly used for this purpose and the data must be sampled at 6-hourly intervals or better.
- ◆ **Real Time Display.** Real time data are used in a day-to-day mode both offshore and onshore to plan and execute operations. These data are often combined with the previous observations, occurrence statistics and forecasts to take decisions on when operations shall start or be cancelled.
- ◆ **Weather forecasts.** Accurate forecasts are needed in all marine operations and they are playing an increasingly important role because operations practically have been extended to all-year activities. Aviation forecasts are another important issue because flying distances have been increased.

Spatial variability is another difficulty with metocean data collection, and this is especially evident for ocean currents. As winds and waves always can be representative for a larger area, the variability in the currents are much greater. A dense net of *in situ* measurements is very expensive and combined with long-term measurements it is evidently constraining.

In order to investigate the mesoscale ocean current variability (both spatial and temporal), an attempt has been done in OPERALT to utilise satellite radar altimeter. This distribution mapping has been carried out by sea surface height anomalies and velocity anomalies. In addition, time series of the sea surface height anomaly have been examined at selected points

by applying Complex Principal Component Analysis. Results studied for the period 1987 – 1995 show significant mesoscale activities in the Faeroe-Shetland Channel and over parts of the Norwegian Continental Shelf and the Voering Plateau. It is apparent that an area of relative high RMS and EKE values (above 8 cm and $300 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^{-1}$) which extends northwards from the Faeroe-Shetland Channel, represents the variability of the Norwegian Atlantic Current and the meanders and eddies developed in this area. The deep ocean basin in the interior of the Norwegian Sea is seen to have low RMS and EKE values.

It is difficult to see that sea surface anomaly derived ocean currents can represent more than quantitative or descriptive results, and it is unlikely that derived values can reach the same accuracy as measured data even after extensive comparisons with *in situ* measurements. This is because the EKE values at best represents a barotropic or geostrophic signal.

However, there are several methods to apply the sea surface anomalies. The following applications can be suggested:

- ◆ The altimeter data will give a descriptive picture of the mesoscale activity over a region and, assuming that the variability over the region is relatively equal, this gives a useful indication of the activities in the requested area.
- ◆ The initial analysis and mapping can be used to decide where to perform representative *in situ* measurements and thereby reduce the risk of making non-representative measurements and later wrong interpretation of the results.
- ◆ In combination with short-term current measurements (≈ 2 months), the altimeter data can indicate if the selected period is typical, if it is likely that extremes are recorded. This reduces the uncertainty about seasonal and annual variability.

Numerical simulation models and current hindcasts have been established for some 'developed' areas and such results are also used for the purpose described above. In this sense, when it comes to the preferred method of choice, the analysis of altimeter data has to be cost-effective.

2.4 Verification plan (WP 2400)

The verification of the altimeter-derived products is done by the following methods:

- Inter-comparison of sea surface elevation and anomaly fields between ERS and Topex/Poseidon data (WP4100)
- Comparison of geostrophic current derived from surface elevation data against measured currents from anchored moorings (WP4200)
- Comparison of geostrophic current derived from surface elevation data against high resolution ocean model simulations (WP4200)
- Overall assessment of the products by Norske Shell (WP4300)

3. Implementation (WP 3000)

The work in the project has focused on analysis of ERS-1 and 2 and Topex/Poseidon data over a six-year period from 1992 to 1998. The investigated area is located west of mid-Norway where met-ocean conditions are investigated by a consortium of oil companies involved in deep sea drilling at depths of more than 1000 m (Figure 3). Norske Shell is leader of this consortium.

Figure 3: Mean T/P tracks (black) and ERS-1/2 tracks (Red) superimposed on the bathymetry of the study area.

The altimeter is a nadir-looking active microwave instrument which transmits short pulses to the sea surface and accurately clocks the time elapsed before the reflected pulses are received at the altimeter antenna. The distance from the antenna to the sea surface is then computed using estimates for the speed of light through the intervening atmospheric column. This distance is subtracted from the height of the antenna above a chosen reference ellipsoid to obtain the height of the sea surface above the ellipsoid. The major unknown components of the sea level estimated in this way are the geoid undulations and the dynamic sea level which is related to ocean current features at different spatial and temporal scales (Figure 4).

Since the geoid is not known to sufficient accuracy in most cases, the normal procedure is to subtract the sea level measurement at a selected time from all other measurements at the same point to obtain the sea level residuals referred to the selected time. This eliminates the geoid

component from the sea level since it is time-invariant, but unfortunately, also the time-invariant part of the dynamic sea level. The temporal mean of the measurements at each point is subsequently subtracted from the instantaneous height residuals to obtain the sea level anomaly referred to the mean sea level. The sea level anomaly thus computed is a very good indicator of mesoscale variability of the ocean current field and provides quantitative information about the location, strength and size of eddies, meanders and fronts, the weakening and strengthening of currents and other mesoscale features. Under the geostrophic assumption, it is also possible to estimate the velocity anomalies from the gradient of the height anomalies, and subsequently, the eddy kinetic energy.

Figure 4. The satellite altimeter measurement principle.

3.1 Mean sea surface estimation (WP 3100)

This task covers the analysis of a high-resolution local altimetric mean sea level for the prime study area. Because of small sea-mounts and trenches, and small scale features not well known, the geoid is not well estimated at scales smaller than 500 km. The sea level anomaly is therefore used by removing a mean sea surface or a mean profile to the altimetric height, a process which eliminates the geoid. For near real time applications, it is essential to have this altimetric mean sea level available prior to commencement of operations. Accordingly, this task was defined to produce a local, precise, high-resolution altimetric mean sea surface in the study area using all available data at the beginning of the task. Mean sea surfaces were estimated using ERS-1 (35 day and 168 day repeat cycles), Topex/Poseidon and GEOSAT data (Fig. 5). The ERS-1 and GEOSAT data were first adjusted to Topex/Poseidon data using a crossover analysis and all three data sets were combined to estimate the respective mean sea surfaces.

Figure 5. Mean sea surface elevation in the North Atlantic and the Norwegian Sea based on Topex/Poseidon (93-95), ERS-1 and GEOSAT Exact Repeat Mission (87-88). The units are in cm (colour bar).

The difference between the mean sea level profile and the CLS-SHOM MSS is calculated for the study area for Topex/Poseidon and ERS SLA data, respectively (Fig. 6). CLS SHOM MSS is the notion for Mean Sea Level with an accuracy of a few centimeters from a 10 years altimeter data set (<http://www.cls.fr/mss>). Since there were some local inconsistencies in the mean sea surface or mean profiles computed from the various satellite missions, it was decided to use separate mean profiles rather than one merged mean sea surface.

Figure 6: Mean along track Sea Level Anomaly minus CLS/SHOM Mean Sea Surface for a) T/P and b) ERS. Units are in cm (colour bar).

3.2 Combined analysis of Topex/Poseidon and ERS data (WP 3200)

The altimeter data used for this study comes from Topex/Poseidon, ERS-1 cersat-1, ERS-1 cersat-2 and ERS-2 cersat-2, from October 1992 to December 1998. T/P has a 10 day repeat cycle and is on a 66° orbit declination. ERS-1/2 has a 35 days repeat cycle and is on a 98° orbit declination. The data from ERS-1 geodetic mission with a 168 day repeat cycle is only used in the construction of the CLS-SHOM mean sea surface, but no Sea Level Anomaly is derived for this cycle since we cannot calculate a mean profile for one 168 day repeat cycle. The maximum coverage of the area by T/P and ERS-1/2 satellites is shown in Figure 3, where the T/P ground tracks are in black (less dense but more frequently repeated), and the ERS-1/2 tracks in red.

3.2.1 Processing applied to the data

In order to merge ERS-1/2 and T/P data, homogeneous altimetric corrections were applied to the data sets and a global crossover minimisation using the more accurate T/P altimeter data as reference was carried out in order to reduce ERS-1/2 orbit error. The data processing can be summarised as follows:

- **Removal of orbit error:** Global cross over minimisation using the more accurate T/P altimeter data as the reference to reduce ERS-1/2 orbit error.
- **Creation of SLA:** Relative to a 3 year mean profile, consistent for T/P and ERS.
- **Filtering of SLA:** Using a loess filter to remove high frequency signal over 63 km for along track calculation of geostrophic velocities, over 35 kilometres to smooth the data before sampling the mapping procedure.
- **Sampling of SLA:** every other data point (every 14 km) from the SLA filtered at 35 km to create super-observations.
- **Mapping of SLA (MSLA):** sub-optimal space and time objective analysis to map the super-observations on to a grid (0.2 degrees in longitude, 0.1 in latitude) using appropriate altimetric data error statistics (10% T/P, 15% ERS) and appropriate correlation scales (15 days - 90 km). Long wavelength errors are also removed (residual orbit error, tide and inverse barometer errors). Mapping errors are also estimated as a results of the method used for the mapping.

3.2.2 Corrections applied to HH T/P data

The along track Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) are obtained from the data corrected for the general geophysical correction which are for TOPEX/POSEIDON (T/P) Homogeneous Historical (HH) data:

- NASA orbit
- altimetric range
- dry tropospheric correction
- inverse barometer correction

- wet tropospheric correction from radiometer (TMR)
- dual frequency ionospheric correction (filtered at 300km) for TOPEX and DORIS for POSEIDON
- sea state bias (BM4, Gaspar et al. 1994)
- correction of the cross-track geoid gradient (by removal of the mean sea surface OSU95)
- correction ocean tide CSR3.0 (Eanes et al., 1995)
- correction land tide
- correction polar tide

3.2.3 Corrections applied to HH ERS-1/2 data

For ERS-1 and 2 homogeneous historical (HH) data the corrections are:

- PDAF orbit
- altimetric range (correction of a dating bias for data from CERSAT 2)
- orbit error correction calculated from adjustment on to T/P at crossover points (Le Traon et al. 1995, 1997)
- dry tropospheric correction (ECMWF)
- inverse barometer correction
- wet tropospheric correction from radiometer (MWR) extrapolated close to the coast
- model ionospheric correction
- sea state bias : -5.5% of $H_{1/3}$ for data from CERSAT 1 and BM3 (Gaspar et al. 1994) for CERSAT 2.
- correction of the cross-track geoid gradient (by removal of the mean sea surface OSU95, (AVISO., 1994)
- correction ocean tide CSR3.0
- correction land tide

3.2.4 Extraction of the along-track sea level anomalies for T/ P and ERS-1/2

From the homogenous inter-calibrated data sets, sea level anomalies are computed relative to the mean sea surface profiles (mean over a period equivalent to 3 years corresponding to the cycles 11 to 121 of T/P) for T/P and ERS-1/2. These data are globally distributed by AVISO. The AVISO altimetry center in France is the French Active Archive Data Center for multi-satellite altimeter missions. AVISO processes, validates and archives above level-2 altimeter data (full Geophysical Data Records) from the T/P mission and distributes them to its user community.

The SLA are subsetted for the area: 55 north to 71 degrees north in latitude and 345 to 15 degrees east in longitude. The real area of interest for OPERALT is smaller but a larger area is extracted in order to avoid edge effects in the mapping.

The SLA are then filtered at 63 kilometres using a Loess filter, in order to remove the high frequency signal that would bring too much noise in the calculation of the geostrophic velocities. These velocities are calculated normal to the passes.

Along track statistics

The along track mean and RMS of SLA anomaly, and EKE derived from the geostrophic velocities are plotted (Figure 7, Figure A13 and Figure A14) for T/P and ERS-1/2 for the different ERS time period: CERSAT-1/ERS-1, CERSAT-2/ERS-1 and CERSAT-2/ERS-2. It shows that overall the along track value of SLA are in good agreement between T/P and ERS data, and that ERS-2 data resolve smaller spatial scales than T/P. The mean SLA between CERSAT-2/ERS-2 and T/P is a bit larger at 0 degree longitude and from 62 to 64 degree north. This is due to the time sampling of the data, where cycle 12 to 37 do not coincide perfectly with T/P cycles 135 to 230. Important oceanic changes appear in a short time, therefore changing the mean.

Mapping of sea level anomalies

The sea level anomalies are also interpolated to a regular time-space grid using an optimal interpolation method which take into account residual correlated noise, specifically adapted to the study area. From the gridded sea level anomalies (Mapped Sea Level Anomalies), geostrophic velocity anomalies are also computed. More specifically, MSLA are calculated from SLA filtered at 35 km. Data are then subsetting one point out of two points to reduce the amount of data for the next processing step. The mapping consists of an inverse method which takes into account the correlation scales in time (15 days) and space (90 kilometres in longitude and in latitude). It couples data from difference satellites (here T/P and ERS) by affecting them a weight depending on the noise (calculated in percent of the signal variance). Here we use 10% for T/P and 15% for ERS. A long wavelength analysis is performed at the same time to remove residual long wavelength errors (such as orbit error, inverse barometer errors) by using a radius of influence three time as large in space as the one defined by the correlation scales and keeping 1 point out of 3 in this large radius of influence. Data are calculated onto a grid of 0.2 degree in longitude and 0.1 degree in latitude. For each grid point a mapping error is estimated. It is a function of the spatial and temporal spread to the grid point time and location of the data used in the estimation. An overview of available SLA maps is given in Table 5, and examples of plots are shown in Appendix A3. Eddy kinetic energy (EKE), which is defined in section 3.3, is derived from the SLA along each track. The mean EKE for October 1992 to December 1993 for both ERS-1 and Topex/Poseidon are shown in Fig. 7 (bottom panel). Seasonal EKE is also plotted for 1993 to 1998 (Figure A15 to Figure A18), along with the seasonal mean (Figure A19 to Figure A22). It shows that the study region off Mid-Norway is very dynamical and that there are large seasonal and interannual variations. Therefore, long the time series are important to have a better description of the overall dynamics of the area.

Figure 7. Statistics for ERS-1/CERSAT-1 and T/P for October 1992 – December 1993. Top: mean SLA, centre: standard deviation of SLA, bottom: Eddy kinetic energy.

Table 5. Available SLA maps

Cycle number for T/P	002-046	047-092	093-136	137-228
ERS data	Cersat-1 ERS-1	None (ERS-1 geodetic mission)	Cersat-2 ERS-1	Cersat-2 ERS-2
Dates for SLA	02/10/92-23/12/93	23/12/93-24/03/95	24/03/95-03/06/96	03/06/96-19/05/99
Julian day / dates of maps	15635-16045 22/10/92-06/12/93	16055-16525 16/12/93-31/03/95	16535-16955 10/04/95-03/06/96	16965-18025 13/06/96-09/05/99
Number of maps	42	48	43	107

3.3 Product development based on SLA data (WP 3300)

The dynamic sea level derived from altimeter measurements is related to the surface current field through the geostrophic equation, which describes non-accelerated motion where the pressure gradient is balanced by the Coriolis force (Fig. 8) and the role of other forces such as wind stress, bottom friction and viscous forces are negligible.

Figure 8. Balance of forces for a geostrophic current directed into the paper.

The equation of motion then reduces to:

$$-fv = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{fp}{fx} \tag{1}$$

$$fu = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{fp}{fy} \tag{2}$$

$$\rho g = -\frac{fp}{fz} \tag{3}$$

where p is the pressure, u, v, are the x- and y- components respectively, of the current velocity, ρ is the density, g the gravitational acceleration, f is the Coriolis parameter, given by $f = 2 \times \Theta \times \sin \phi$, where Θ is the earth's angular velocity and φ is the latitude. Integrating equation 3 and substituting in equation 1 and equation 2 gives

$$v = -\frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x}$$

$$u = \frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial y}$$

where ζ is the height of the sea surface. Thus geostrophic velocities are related to the sea surface slopes in a direction normal to the currents. For a typical western boundary current, with a current speed of 1 ms^{-1} , surface slopes are of the order of 1 m per 100 km.

In the case of mesoscale eddies and meanders, the geostrophic balance will be modified by the centrifugal forces resulting from the curvature of the flow field.

$$v_{\theta r} = -\frac{rf}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{r^2 f^2}{4} + rg \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial r}}$$

where r is the radius of curvature. For the same sea surface slopes, gradient current speeds are higher than geostrophic current speeds when the flow is anticyclonic motion and lower than geostrophic current speeds when the flow is cyclonic.

Wind stresses, bottom friction, viscous forces, etc complicates the balance of forces and give rise to accelerated motion. However, in such cases where the geostrophic balance does not strictly apply, the surface slopes can be used to extract the geostrophic component of the total current velocity.

The following products from altimeter data have been developed in the project:

- *Maps of the distribution of Eddy Kinetic Energy*
- *Maps of the distribution of Reynolds Stresses*
- *Time series of SLA at selected locations*
- *Ten-day averaged maps of SLA overlaid with geostrophic velocity anomaly vectors.*
- *Ten-day averaged velocity anomaly maps combined with instantaneous SAR image and/or velocity component normal to individual altimeter tracks.*
- *Time variability of SLA and velocity anomalies for individual tracks*
- *Sea wave height*
- *Wind speed*

Examples of these products are shown in sections 3.3.1 to 3.3.8

3.3.1 Maps of the distribution of Eddy Kinetic Energy

These are derived from the mapped geostrophic velocity anomaly data. Eddy Kinetic Energy at each grid point is calculated as the sum of squares of the magnitude of the velocity anomaly ($1/2 \langle uu \rangle$ where $\langle uu \rangle$ is the RMS of geostrophic velocity normal to the passes over a certain time period) and plotted as a contour plot showing the distribution of this temporally averaged parameter in space. The maps give a good quantitative estimate of the magnitude of the mesoscale variability and identifies locations where it is higher than the nominal values.

Figure 9 shows the seasonal distributions of eddy kinetic energy (EKE) computed from the merged T/P and ERS data during the 6-year period from October 1992 to September 1998. The EKE distribution provides an indication of areas with enhanced mesoscale activity, in the form of eddies, fronts, meandering currents as well as variations in the strengths of the current. The plots show high EKE (above $100 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) along the path of the Norwegian Atlantic Current, with highest values (up to $200 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) seen within the Faroe-Shetland Channel. This is to be expected, as mesoscale activity is generally higher in the neighbourhood of strong currents, which often interact with the topography to generate meanders and eddies. It is particularly interesting to see that altimetry detects high EKE to the north of the Faroes, confirming the recent observations of significant inflow of Atlantic water around the Faroes (Hansen et al., 1986). In the Norwegian Sea, there are pockets of high EKE centred around $63^\circ\text{N}; 5^\circ\text{E}$ and $64.5^\circ\text{N}; 3.5^\circ\text{E}$. These regions overlap the locations of the deep water licensing areas, Ormen Lange, Møre Vest and Helland Hansen. EKE is low over most of the deep basin of the Norwegian Sea, the northern reaches of the North Sea and in the near-shore areas north of 64°N , where no significant mesoscale activity has been reported.

The plots also reveal significant seasonal variability in the EKE distributions. There is a tendency for enhanced activity over large parts of the study area in the winter half-year (October-March) compared to the summer half-year (April-September). However, while EKE is high overall during January-March, these high values persist only in the Norwegian Sea during April-June – in the neighbourhood of the Faroes, high EKE is limited to very narrow pockets during this season. These pockets spread to the north of the Faroes during July-December, while over most of the Norwegian Sea, this is a low-activity period. The overall picture that emerges is of enhanced mesoscale activity in the Faroe-Shetland Channel during July-September, moving northwards with the Norwegian Atlantic Current to extend over most of its path including the retroflexion southwards along the Norwegian coast in Jan-Mar, and then slowing down, first in the southern parts.

Figure 9. Seasonal maps of the distribution of Eddy Kinetic Energy in the study area

Figure 9. (cont.)

3.3.2 Maps of the distribution of Reynolds Stresses

Theory of Reynolds stress

The Reynolds stress is a stress exerted by the turbulent fluctuation on the mean flow. It can also be interpreted as the rate of mean momentum transfer by turbulent fluctuations. If the turbulent fluctuations are completely isotropic, if they have no directional preference, the off-diagonal components of $\overline{u'v'}$ vanish, and $\overline{u'^2} = \overline{v'^2} = \overline{w'^2}$.

The Reynolds equation for x-component of velocity is as follows:

$$\frac{d\bar{u}}{dt} = -\bar{\alpha} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x} + 2\Omega \sin \phi \bar{v} - 2\Omega \cos \phi \bar{w} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial z^2} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \overline{u'u'} - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \overline{u'v'} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \overline{u'w'}$$

A term such as $\nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial x^2} \right)$ can be written as $\partial / (\nu \partial \bar{u} / \partial x) \partial x$, and $\rho \nu (\partial \bar{u} / \partial x)$ is the stress in the direction due to molecular effects and a gradient of $\bar{u}$ in the x-direction. We can therefore identify $-\rho \overline{u'u'}$ as a stress due to the turbulence, termed Reynolds stresses.

Examples of Reynolds stress maps

The gridded data set of sea level anomalies also allows an examination of the directional properties of the mesoscale variability. This is presented in the Reynolds Stress distributions for the 4 seasons as presented in Figure 10. The arrows represent the direction along which variability is maximum (direction of principal variance) and the direction normal to it at each point, with the length of the arrows indicating the magnitude of the variances. In an isotropic field, the magnitude of the variance would be equal in all directions. The plots presented, however, show a significant degree of anisotropy, as would be expected in an area dominated by a relatively strong current. In the Norwegian Sea, there is a clear tendency for the directions of principal variance to be aligned along the depth contours along the core of the Norwegian Atlantic Current. This could be interpreted to imply that the position of the core current is relatively fixed, with variability being mainly due to strengthening and weakening of the mean current, rather than due to meanders. Towards the seaward edges of the current, the variances are lower, and the field is more isotropic, an indication of the meandering nature of the current here. This is also the case in the Faroe-Shetland Channel, where the mesoscale variability is large, but more or less isotropic, indicating that the current does not have a narrow and steady core here as is the case further northwards. The above description holds irrespective of the seasons. The only seasonal differences in the Reynold's Stress distribution is in the magnitude of the variability, rather than in the directionality. In the Faroe-Shetland Channel, isotropy seems to become more evident during July to December.

Figure 10. Seasonal maps of the distribution of Reynolds Stresses in the study area

Figure 10. (cont.)

3.3.3 Time series of SLA at selected locations

Time series of sea level anomalies are extracted from altimeter data for selected geographical locations in relevance to offshore platforms. Examples of such time series are shown in Fig. 11. Point 1 in the map (Fig. 11a) represents the location of Ormen Lange and Point 10 the location of the Voering Platau.

A significant feature of the time series in c) and d) is the seasonal maxima in late winter at the Vøring Plateau both in 1987 – 1989 (during the Geosat period) and in 1995 – 1997 (from ERS-2 data). At Ormen Lange no such seasonal signal is evident in Fig. 11 b. The SLA data can be used to study correlation of signals between different locations and investigate possible propagation of signals along the North Atlantic Current due to eddies, Kelvin waves or other low-frequency oceanographic phenomena.

Figure 11. Examples of time series of SLA at two selected locations indicated on the map (a). The Topex/Poseidon data at Ormen Lange (b); Geosat data at Voering Plateau, (c) and ERS-2 data at Voering Plateau, (d).

3.3.4 Ten-day averaged maps of SLA overlaid with geostrophic velocity anomaly vectors

The along track sea level anomalies can be interpolated to regular space-time grid, where the cross track spacing and the repeat period are used to determine appropriate grid sizes. For Topex/Poseidon these can be presented as ten day averaged maps of sea level anomalies overlaid with geostrophic velocity vectors calculated from the sea surface slopes, with a spatial grid of 26 km, as shown in Fig. 12. The interpolation method and the plots have been presented in NERSC Technical Report No 140 (Haugen et al., 1998).

Figure 12. Ten-day averaged maps of SLA and geostrophic velocity anomaly vectors and SLA (red: high, geen/blue: low)

3.3.5 Ten-day averaged velocity anomaly maps combined with instantaneous SAR image and/or velocity component normal to individual altimeter tracks

The ERS-2 SAR image acquired over an area south-west of Ormen Lange shows very clear frontal structures, oriented in a north-westerly direction and in spirals indicating eddies (Figure 13). Topex/Poseidon altimeter track no. 144 crossed these features about 6 hours before the SAR image was taken.

Figure 13. ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 27.09.97, overlaid with altimeter along-track sea level anomalies (coloured dots), cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies (green arrows), and mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies (red arrows).

The SLA and cross-track velocity indicates that the central part of the SAR image is a frontal zone with southward velocities on the left and northward velocities on the right. Moreover, the mapped geostrophic velocities averaged over 10 days show a cyclonic eddy which agrees with the cross track velocity from track no 144. The SAR image also shows a cyclonic eddy further to the north east. Direct agreement between instantaneous SAR mapping and averaged estimate from 10 days of altimeter data can not be expected, especially because the eddies are propagating with the mean current in this area. The along-track sea level anomalies and cross-track velocity anomalies along track 144 are shown both for the repeat passes and as contour plots in distance-time space (Figure 14).

A direct comparison between altimeter derived currents and SAR image features is difficult because the temporal and spatial coverage and resolution of the two systems are quite different. While SAR is capable of observing snapshots of features with scales down to a few hundreds of meters, the altimeter provides sea level heights along the satellite tracks with a sampling distance of about 7 km. By combining data from several tracks over a time interval of at least 10 days, it is possible to establish geostrophic velocity anomaly maps resolving current features with scales of a few tens of kilometers. This implies that the altimeter can observe current features which are persistent and stationary over at least 10 days. Altimeter data can not capture short-lived mesoscale features observed by SAR. On the other hand, the temporal SAR sampling, which is at best three days, is not good enough to follow the evolution of the short-lived features.

The temporal sampling is also a problem in deriving the altimeter sea level anomalies. The lack of an adequate geoid makes it necessary to subtract a temporal mean from the altimeter height measurements. The 10 (35) day sampling interval of the Topex/Poseidon (ERS) altimeter is hardly adequate to resolve mesoscale variability in the study area, where temporal scales of eddies can be as short as a few days. Consequently, the mean that is subtracted from the time series of seas level measurements will be contaminated by variability at these unresolved temporal scales.

Since SAR is a side-looking instrument and altimeter is a nadir-looking instrument, it is not feasible to obtain simultaneous observations from the two instruments from the same satellite. In our case, it has been possible to use altimeter tracks of the T/P crossing ERS-2 SAR swath within 1-2 days of each other. This approach has been used to compare SAR current features imaged with geostrophic current estimates from altimeter. More examples of combined SAR and altimeter data are given in Appendix A2 (Figs. A1-A3).

3.3.6 Time variability of SLA and velocity anomalies for individual tracks.

Figure 14. The time resolution of the profiles is determined by the satellite repeat cycle which in this case is 10 days. The profiles can show if a signal like an eddy propagates through the altimeter track slowly enough to be observed by at least two profiles.

Figure 14. The along-track sea level anomalies and cross-track velocity anomalies for track 144.

3.3.7. Significant wave height

The significant wave height is obtained by the analysis of the shape and intensity of the radar wave after reflection on the sea surface (return signal). When the waves are big, the return signal is wide spread in time. Inversely, when the sea is flat, the return signal is narrower. Examples of significant wave height estimates are shown in Fig. 15.

Figure 15: Significant Wave Height from T/P and ERS-2 every 10 days (based on T/P cycle).

3.3.8. Wind speed

Altimeter wind speed model function is purely empirical (Witter and Chelton 1991), based on the relations between the mean square sea surface slope and the wind speed. It depends on the backscatter coefficient σ_0 according to the relation: $U = \sum a_n (\sigma_0)^2$, where U is wind speed and a_n $n=1,5$ are polynomial coefficients from the least-square fit of a 5th order polynomial to the modified Chelton and Wentz wind speed tabular model. Examples of wind speed estimates are shown in Fig. 16.

Figure 16: Wind at 10 meters every 10 days from T/P and ERS-2 (based on T/P cycle)

4. Validation and Verification (WP 4000)

4.1 Validation by intercomparison (WP 4100)

4.1.1 Intercomparison of HH T/P and ERS-1/2 data to check for coherence

To combine T/P and ERS-1/2 data, it is first necessary to have homogeneous and inter-calibrated data sets. The homogeneity between the two data sets can be evaluated through the temporal RMS of the difference (T/P) – (ERS-1/2) of MSLA over the 5 year period going from October 1992 to December 1993 and from April 1995 to November 1998 (Figure 17). Homogeneous corrections between T/P and ERS-1/2 are applied and ERS SSH are adjusted to the more precise T/P data using the global minimisation of T/P and ERS crossover difference. It can be seen that the higher discrepancy lies close to the coasts due to a difference in data availability between T/P and ERS-1/2 (see next chapter), and in areas where the signal is at small scale. The latter discrepancies are expected due to the difference of sampling in the two altimeters.

Figure 17. Root-Mean-Square of the SLA difference between T/P and ERS-1/2 (in centimetre), showing the coherence of the two data sets over a 5-year period.

4.1.2 Validation by intercomparison of NRT and HH data.

A set of statistics over 3 months, from April 7 to July 6 1999 is displayed for HH and NRT data (see Figure 18 – 21). It shows that there is a difference in mean due primarily to the difference in data used for the mapping between HH and NRT data.

Figure 18: Mean MSLA field over the period April 7, 1999 to July 6, 1999 for a) HH T/P data, b) NRT T/P, c) HH ERS-2, d) NRT ERS-2, e) HH T/P+ERS-2 and f) NRT T/P+ERS-2. Scales are from -15 to 5 cm.

Figure 19: RMS of the MSLA field over the period April 7, 1999 to July 6, 1999 for a) HH T/P data, b) NRT T/P, c) HH ERS-2, d) NRT ERS-2, e) HH T/P+ERS-2 and f) NRT T/P+ERS-2. Scales are from 0 to 15 cm.

Table 6: Statistics on the maps of the mean MSLA over SLA April 7 – July 6, 1999 for NRT and HH data from T/P, ERS-2 and the combination of T/P and ERS-2.

April 7 – July 6, 1999 MEAN	Mean of the map	Square root of the variance of the map of the temporal mean
MEAN HH SLA over spring 1999 (cm)		
T/P	-2.93	2.11
ERS-2	-4.56	2.22
T/P and ERS-2 combined	-3.36	2.00
MEAN NRT SLA over spring 1999 (cm)		
T/P	-1.64	2.07
ERS-2	-1.68	1.80
T/P and ERS-2 combined	-1.59	1.99

The key statistical figures of the MSLA maps calculate for the three-month study period in 1999 are summarised in Table 6. Figure 18 shows that the mean is lower for HH data than for NRT data. The most likely reason is that the maps for HH and for NRT do not use exactly the same amount of data due to the more rudimentary elimination of spurious data and the variable acquisition delays (but mostly 48 hours for T/P, 72 for ERS-2) for NRT data. Furthermore the signals are rapidly changing in time, and this biases the results by increasing or lowering the temporal mean. The most inconsistent temporal mean is for ERS-2 data, which can have larger gaps in data within a 21 day period than T/P data that have a more homogenous spatial distribution in the same lap of time. Fig. 19 shows the temporal RMS of the MSLA fields corresponding to the same data as in Fig. 18.

The temporal variance of the signal (Figure 20) shows however that the signals seen by T/P and ERS-2 have similar variance, although NRT has a larger variance than HH data which comes from the fact that NRT data are noisier than HH data.. An example of a SLA map from ERS-2 on a specific day, June 23, 1999 (Figure 21) shows the difference between HH and NRT on one singular map, and specific attention is paid to the error in percent of the signal variance: it is almost double for NRT than for HH (respectively 43% and 29% in average), with the typical diamond shape outlines, illustrating lower errors under the tracks and higher errors between tracks, and more generally in area devoid of data. It really emphasise the area around the islands and along the Norwegian coast with few data points. Missing data have an impact on errors and in the mapping as seen previously. It renders long wavelength bias harder to estimate, therefore a less accurate correction of long wavelength errors, and a lesser accuracy of the final results. Another difference between HH and NRT processing is time window in the mapping: the map is centered at T+/- 10 days for HH MSLA, and T+5/-15 days for NRT MSLA. This de-centering of the NRT MSLA is chosen as a compromise between the time delay acceptable for the map and a reasonable accuracy of the results. Part of the difference in the geographical mean between HH and NRT SLA (Figure 21a, Figure 21b and Figure 21c) is due to the fact that a different ensemble of data is used to do the mapping, and as the signal varies very rapidly from a week to the next, it leads to

Figure 20: Variance of the MSLA field over the period April 7, 1999 to July 6, 1999 for a) HH T/P data, b) NRT T/P, c) HH ERS-2, d) NRT ERS-2, e) HH T/P+ERS-2 and f) NRT T/P+ERS-2. Scales are from 0 to 90 cm.

Figure 21. ERS-2 for June 23, 1999 for: a) HH MSLA, b) NRT MSLA, c) NRT-HH MSLA, d) HH mapping error, and e) NRT mapping error.

differences in the mapping. The square root of the variance is only slightly larger in the case of NRT data (3.94 cm versus 3.47 cm for HH) which shows that both signal varies in a similar fashion.

Lastly, a retracking is performed on ERS-2 OPR data, but not on FDP data. The retracking is performed to obtain a better estimation of the distance (midpoint of the waveform) measured by the altimeter. The impact is at small scale, specifically in areas of rapid changes in the geoid. It is higher than 2.25 cm between Iceland and Scotland. Furthermore, instrumental noise is larger at high latitude it is harder to determine accurately the slope of the waveform since the wave are more intense at high latitudes than low latitudes. By high pass filtering the FDP and OPR SLA at 207 kilometres, the RMS of the difference of SLA over 5 ERS cycles is on average 2.25 cm.

As a summary, direct statistics of the temporal difference of HH and NRT maps for T/P, ERS-2 and T/P+ERS-2 for April 7, 1999 to July 6, 1999 are displayed on Figure A4 to Figure A12 and are summarized in Table 7. The eddy kinetic energy difference between NRT and HH is a measurement of the accuracy of the geostrophic velocities. Smaller scale patterns appear on the ERS-2 maps, with is in agreement with the denser spatial sampling of ERS-2, and also in agreement with the fact that ERS-2 HH and NRT are more different (retracking performed on HH, not on NRT, different orbit used wet tropospheric correction from radiometer for HH, model for NRT – this is being revised and radiometer data will soon be used in NRT (FDP) correction).

Table 7: Statistics on the maps of the temporal statics over 6 months of the difference between NRT and HH data for T/P, ERS-2 and the combination of T/P and ERS-2.

April 7 – July 6, 1999	Mean of the map	Square root of the variance of the map of the temporal mean
MEAN NRT-HH SLA over spring 1999 (cm)		
T/P	1.29	0.54
ERS-2	4.74	1.28
T/P and ERS-2 combined	3.15	0.98
RMS of NRT-HH SLA over spring 1999 (cm)		
T/P	1.29	0.54
ERS-2	2.88	1.74
T/P and ERS-2 combined	1.77	0.95
NRT-HH SLA EKE over spring 1999 (cm²/sec²)		
T/P	12.36	11.44
ERS-2	45.29	29.48
T/P and ERS-2 combined	27.99	32.10

Statistics on the MSLA difference between NRT and HH T/P and ERS-2 combined data for the period 7 April 1999 to 6 July 1999 are displayed in (Figure A4 to Figure A12). The overall NRT-HH SLA for T/P and ERS-2 combined mean over the 3 months is 1.77 centimetres, and the overall NRT-HH SLA RMS is 3.15 cm for the same time period. The larger differences are found close to the coasts, where data are interpolated since the satellite tracks do not reach the coasts (see Figure 3).

4.2 Validation against field measurements (WP 4200)

For a more rigorous validation of altimeter data, time series of in situ current observations in the altimeter data points is required. The field data should be acquired over a duration of several years, so that the annual mean can be eliminated in the same way that the mean is subtracted from the altimeter data. In addition, since it is not obvious what depth layer the geostrophic velocities derived from the altimeter sea level anomalies represent, it is necessary to have current measurements from different depths. No dedicated measurement programme was included in this project to support such a rigorous validation exercise. Therefore, we had to use sub-optimal data collected under other projects, made available via Norske Shell and Geophysical Institute of University of Bergen, Norway.

The best available data set for the validation was the current meter data collected by the Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen, from 4 current meter moorings along the so-called Svinøy Section off the Møre coast of Norway. This is an area where the confluence in the shelf break result in a merging of different branches of the Atlantic inflow to the Norwegian Sea and the section cuts through the core of the inflow. The measurements began in April 1995 and have continued on a regular basis till today (Skagseth, Orvik and Mork, 1997).

The validation was carried out in collaboration with the Geophysical Institute. The current meter data corresponding to the altimeter measurement times were extracted from the full time series after removing the main tidal components. The temporal mean of the current meter data was computed and subtracted from the data. Subsequently, the component of the current vector in the direction normal to the altimeter track was computed. The altimeter cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies at 13 data points along the track were then submitted along with the cross-track velocity anomalies extracted from the 4 current meter moorings for different depths for a cross-correlation analysis. The locations of the current meter moorings and the altimeter data points used in the comparison are shown in Figure 22.

The results of the correlation analysis are shown in tabular form for the 4 different moorings in Tables 8 to 11. The current meter measurements are denoted by the mooring name and the depth of the current meter (for example, s1-100 is the current meter measurement at 100 m depth from mooring S1). The altimeter data points are denoted by the point number along Topex/Poseidon Track 42 followed by v (for example, 06v is altimeter point 6). The cross-

Figure 22. Location of the current meter moorings S1, S2, E1 and E2 and the altimeter data points 5 to 18 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42, in relation to the depth contours (yellow: shallow shelf area; green-blue: deep water areas).

The correlation coefficients between the altimeter geostrophic velocities and the cross track velocity component from the current meters are not particularly high. The highest correlation seen is 0.65 between s1-300 and 07v and 08v. In contrast, the cross-correlation between e1-100 and e1-300 is 0.89 and that between 08v and 09v is 0.94. This is only to be expected in view of 1) the distance between the moorings and the altimeter pass, 2) the spatial averaging over several kms implicitly carried out in the altimeter and 3) the fact that the altimeter measurement is based on the geostrophic approximation, while the current meter measures the total current.

measurement is based on the geostrophic approximation, while the current meter measures the total current.

Apart from the low cross-correlation coefficients, however, there are some interesting characteristics in the structure of the cross-correlation matrix. The most obvious is that the correlation is significantly higher for altimeter data points which are approximately over the same depth contours as the current meter. For instance, for S1, best correlation is obtained for 6, 7 & 8, which may be seen from Figure 22 to be over approximately the same depth contour as S1. For S2, which is deployed in a little deeper water, best correlation is obtained for points 7, 8 & 9. For E1, the best correlation is obtained for points 9, 10 & 11, and for E2, points 11, 12 & 13 provide the best correlation. In at least some of the cases, these are not the altimeter data points that are closest in distance to the mooring in question. This is an important result, because it supports the hypothesis that the currents in this region are steered by the topography. The alignment of the altimeter pass is advantageous to the validation study, because the cross-track direction, along which the geostrophic velocities are computed are almost parallel to the depth contours. This implies that the cross-track velocity component contains the dominant part of the velocity vector.

Another interesting result is that the correlation with the altimeter data is consistently higher for the current meter measurements at 300 m depth than for the measurements at 100 m depth. In the case of mooring S2, the correlation for points 6, 7 & 8 are over 60 % higher (0.54 to 0.57) against the current meter at 300 m depth than against that at 100 m depth (0.33 to 0.35). The reason for this surprising result is probably that the current meter measurements at 100 m depth are more affected by wind and other transient forcing which the altimeter processing eliminate. Thus, despite being a sea surface measurement, sea level anomalies are representative of the current structure of the whole water column.

The velocity time series from one of the current meter moorings, S1 at depth 100 m and 300 m, and 2 altimeter data points 6 and 7 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42, which showed the best correlation are presented in Figure 23. It can be seen that the altimeter cross-track velocity anomalies generally fall within the range of variability of the current meter data and in most cases follow the peaks and valleys in the time series very well. A scatter plot of the current mooring S1 at depth 300 and altimeter data point 8 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42 is seen in Figure 24. These represented the current mooring and altimeter point of best correlation.

The velocity time series from 4 other current meter moorings and 3 altimeter data points for each mooring which showed the best correlation are shown in Figures A23 to A26 and be seen that the altimeter cross-track velocity anomalies generally fall within the range of variability of the current meter data and in most cases follow the peaks and valleys in the time series very well.

Table 8: Cross-correlation matrix for the current meter mooring S1 (depths 100, 300 & 480 m) and altimeter data points 5-11 along Topex/Poseidon track 42.

	s1-100	s1-300	s1-480	05v	06v	07v	08v	09v	10v	11v
s1-100	1.00	0.79	0.34	0.43	0.50	0.54	0.54	0.49	0.38	0.22
s1-300	0.79	1.00	0.56	0.57	0.62	0.65	0.65	0.60	0.47	0.26
s1-480	0.34	0.56	1.00	0.39	0.43	0.47	0.49	0.50	0.48	0.41
05v	0.43	0.57	0.39	1.00	0.97	0.86	0.66	0.40	0.16	-0.03
06v	0.50	0.62	0.43	0.97	1.00	0.96	0.81	0.58	0.32	0.07
07v	0.54	0.65	0.47	0.86	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.78	0.53	0.22
08v	0.54	0.65	0.49	0.66	0.81	0.94	1.00	0.94	0.74	0.43
09v	0.49	0.60	0.50	0.40	0.58	0.78	0.94	1.00	0.92	0.67
10v	0.38	0.47	0.48	0.16	0.32	0.53	0.74	0.92	1.00	0.89
11v	0.22	0.26	0.41	-0.03	0.07	0.22	0.43	0.67	0.89	1.00

Table 9: Cross-correlation matrix for the current meter mooring S2 (depths 100, & 300 m) and altimeter data points 5-12 along Topex/Poseidon track 42.

	s2-100	s2-300	05v	06v	07v	08v	09v	10v	11v	12v
s2-100	1.00	0.61	0.23	0.28	0.33	0.35	0.33	0.28	0.19	0.06
s2-300	0.61	1.00	0.41	0.48	0.55	0.57	0.54	0.45	0.29	0.10
05v	0.23	0.41	1.00	0.97	0.86	0.66	0.40	0.16	-0.03	-0.12
06v	0.28	0.48	0.97	1.00	0.96	0.81	0.58	0.32	0.07	-0.11
07v	0.33	0.55	0.86	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.78	0.53	0.22	-0.06
08v	0.35	0.57	0.66	0.81	0.94	1.00	0.94	0.74	0.43	0.05
09v	0.33	0.54	0.40	0.58	0.78	0.94	1.00	0.92	0.67	0.27
10v	0.28	0.45	0.16	0.32	0.53	0.74	0.92	1.00	0.89	0.57
11v	0.19	0.29	-0.03	0.07	0.22	0.43	0.67	0.89	1.00	0.87
12v	0.06	0.10	-0.12	-0.11	-0.06	0.05	0.27	0.57	0.87	1.00

Table 10: Cross-correlation matrix for the current meter mooring E1 (depths 100 & 300 m) and altimeter data points 5-13 along Topex/Poseidon track 42.

	e1-100	e1-300	05v	06v	07v	08v	09v	10v	11v	12v	13v
e1-100	1.00	0.89	0.22	0.26	0.30	0.33	0.34	0.36	0.36	0.31	0.19
e1-300	0.89	1.00	0.26	0.29	0.32	0.34	0.36	0.37	0.36	0.29	0.17
05v	0.22	0.26	1.00	0.97	0.86	0.66	0.40	0.16	-0.03	-0.12	-0.13
06v	0.26	0.29	0.97	1.00	0.96	0.81	0.58	0.32	0.07	-0.11	-0.19
07v	0.30	0.32	0.86	0.96	1.00	0.94	0.78	0.53	0.22	-0.06	-0.24
08v	0.33	0.34	0.66	0.81	0.94	1.00	0.94	0.74	0.43	0.05	-0.23
09v	0.34	0.36	0.40	0.58	0.78	0.94	1.00	0.92	0.67	0.27	-0.10
10v	0.36	0.37	0.16	0.32	0.53	0.74	0.92	1.00	0.89	0.57	0.17
11v	0.36	0.36	-0.03	0.07	0.22	0.43	0.67	0.89	1.00	0.87	0.55
12v	0.31	0.29	-0.12	-0.11	-0.06	0.05	0.27	0.57	0.87	1.00	0.88
13v	0.19	0.17	-0.13	-0.19	-0.24	-0.23	-0.10	0.17	0.55	0.88	1.00

Table 11: Cross-correlation matrix for the current meter mooring E2 (depths 100 & 300 m) and altimeter data points 7-15 along Topex/Poseidon track 42.

	e2-100	e2-300	07v	08v	09v	10v	11v	12v	13v	14v	15v
e2-100	1.00	0.86	0.14	0.15	0.21	0.32	0.48	0.56	0.51	0.39	0.22
e2-300	0.86	1.00	0.25	0.27	0.35	0.48	0.59	0.61	0.56	0.45	0.23
07v	0.14	0.25	1.00	0.94	0.78	0.53	0.22	-0.06	-0.24	-0.29	-0.26
08v	0.15	0.27	0.94	1.00	0.94	0.74	0.43	0.05	-0.23	-0.35	-0.36
09v	0.21	0.35	0.78	0.94	1.00	0.92	0.67	0.27	-0.10	-0.32	-0.40
10v	0.32	0.48	0.53	0.74	0.92	1.00	0.89	0.57	0.17	-0.14	-0.32
11v	0.48	0.59	0.22	0.43	0.67	0.89	1.00	0.87	0.55	0.20	-0.08
12v	0.56	0.61	-0.06	0.05	0.27	0.57	0.87	1.00	0.88	0.61	0.30
13v	0.51	0.56	-0.24	-0.23	-0.10	0.17	0.55	0.88	1.00	0.90	0.67
14v	0.39	0.45	-0.29	-0.35	-0.32	-0.14	0.20	0.61	0.90	1.00	0.92
15v	0.22	0.23	-0.26	-0.36	-0.40	-0.32	-0.08	0.30	0.67	0.92	1.00

Figure 23 Time series of cross-track current anomalies from the current meter mooring S1 (depths 100 and 300 m) and altimeter data points 6-7 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42.

Figure 24. Scatter plot of coincident current mooring data from S1 at depth 300 and altimeter data at point 8 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42.

4.3 Validation against model simulations (WP 4200)

The eddy kinetic energy have been estimated from the Diadem2 model simulations in the Norwegian Sea (Evensen, 1999) and is shown in Figure 25. The Diadem2 model is based on the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM), originally developed by Rainer Bleck and coworkers at the University of Miami (Bleck et al., 1992). It differs from traditional models by the choice of vertical co-ordinate which is potential density. The use of an orthogonal curvilinear grid allows for the use of a large model domain where high resolution is still retained in the Norwegian Sea area. The model grid is based on a mapping of the poles to two new locations on the earth. The mapping conserves orthogonality for all the grid cells which are all quadratic. The algorithm is presented in (Bentsen et. al., 1999). The Diadem2 model version includes all of the Arctic and has a resolution of approximately 20-25 km along the Gulf Stream extension and down to 10 km in the North Sea. In addition there is a Diadem1 model version with half of this resolution which has been used in this (phase one) project for numerical efficiency.

The eddy kinetic energy from the Diadem2 simulations is not exactly comparable with the EKE from the altimeter data, which has a resolution of $0.2^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$, but should indicate high model variability in the same areas as seen by the altimeter data. The model resolution is too coarse to properly represent the eddy variability in the Nordic Seas. In Figure 30 the variability from a higher resolution (7 km) regional model for the Atlantic Margin is shown. The model shows high EKE along the path of the Norwegian Atlantic Current, which is the same areas as computed from the merged T/P and ERS data during the 6-year period from October 1992 to September (Figure 9), although it is lower in the model than for the observations. EKE is low over most of the deep basin of the Norwegian Sea, as observed from the altimeter data.

This model is run in a nested mode with the Diadem2 model. Clearly with this resolution the model provides a significantly higher variability which is more in agreement with the observations. We expect that a resolution of less than 4 km is needed in order to properly represent all the mesoscale activity in the Nordic Seas but this is presently not feasible in a sophisticated data assimilation system running on available computers.

Thus, the major result from the comparison between the model and altimeter derived circulation is that both the Diadem1 and the Diadem2 models are too coarse for a direct intercomparison between altimeter and model results. On the other hand, the models and observations provides similar locations for the high and low variability areas, and the large scale structures in the observations seems to match well with the model results.

Figure 25. Eddy kinetic energy averaged over a year from a high resolution (7 km) regional Atlantic Margin model.

4.4 Verification of project results (WP 4300)

The OPERALT project was conceived based on promising results obtained in the Norwegian Deepwater Programme (NDP), and the assessment of the OPERALT results is therefore in many ways complementary to results from this programme. The selection of the OPERALT study area and the validation of results are two issues with apparent relevance. In addition, the evaluation of general results must be seen in light of the extreme environmental conditions found in this exposed area of the northeastern Atlantic margin. This means that altimeter products developed in this project could be more advantageous in areas with milder wind and wave climate and less baroclinic effects. The slope areas off West Africa and Brazil should be examples of such regions.

The main purpose of the NDP Metocean Project was to obtain best possible information on ocean currents in the deepwater areas off Norway and a series of activities on data acquisition, modelling, remote sensing and studies were performed. The concept to link ocean current information derived from satellite altimeter data with specific measurements and ocean current model data was initiated from the needs to have simultaneous current information over a large area of eight degrees (60°N to 68°N). It was impossible to have measurements in more than one cross-section at the same time because of cost and capacity restrictions.

The OPERALT study area was selected to extend from 60°N to 66°N and 10°W to 10°E. The northerly extension was chosen to match the Topex/Poseidon boundary but little information was lost due to this. More important, however, was that the study area included the waters between the Faeroes and Shetland. This area is the entrance of warm Atlantic water to the Norwegian Sea and the Norwegian Atlantic Current following the north bound continental slope. The temporal and spatial variations of this region are important for conditions further to the north.

Overall objective:

To develop pre-operational satellite radar altimeter analysis and archival system

It has been demonstrated that altimeter data from Topex/Poseidon and ERS-1/2 can provide quantitative information on ocean currents, both annual/seasonal statistics using data over several years to estimate eddy kinetic energy, and near real time analysis where data over 10 days are used to make current maps.

....and to assess the benefits and cost-effectiveness of the information provided by such system for applications related to offshore operations.

One important customer group for ocean current data, a consortium of oil companies working in deep waters off the coast of Norway, has been actively involved in the project, testing the results of the altimeter data against other current data from the study area. The consortium of oil companies has assessed the current information from altimeter data to be interesting and useful, but more studies are needed to validate the technique. Altimeter data will be used in future ocean current investigations because the data are cost-effective and provide important complementary information relative to standard ocean current measurement techniques.

The specific objectives of the OPERALT project were outlined in five points:

1. To produce an accurate high-resolution local altimetric mean sea level.
2. To produce merged ERS-1/2 and Topex/Poseidon data sets.
3. To validate altimeter-derived current estimates against *in situ* measurements.
4. To develop appropriate altimeter data products.
5. To assess the benefits and cost-effectiveness of Near Real Time (NRT) as well as off-line altimeter data products.

This chapter deals with the objective items and they are addressed separately below.

Accurate high-resolution altimetric mean sea level

This has been done and provides the basis for further analysis of the altimeter data

Merged ERS-1/2 and Topex/Poseidon data sets

All results have shown that there are large seasonal and yearly variations of the oceanographic regime in the study area. This demonstrates the importance of having long time series and consequently confirms the effort to merge altimeter data from different missions. By applying sets of corrections to get intercalibrated data, it has been possible to combine available altimeter products from Topex/Poseidon and ERS-1/2 with reasonable accuracy (historical homogeneous (HH) data).

The Near Real Time (NRT) data was also checked against the more precise HH data from Topex/Poseidon and ERS-2, and the accuracy was found to be acceptable. With a time delay of only days for the NRT products, this implies that NRT data can be used in different modes than the HH data. Forecasts of current phenomena can be one of them. There are some evidence that certain events associated with high variability propagate 'downstream' in slope currents, which means that conditions in the Faeroe – Shetland Channel might be used as a 'reference area' for events occurring further to the north in the Norwegian sector. Because of relative slow oceanic processes, compared with the atmospheric circulation, it should be possible to utilise NRT data for this purpose. To test out this hypothesis could be an item for a new research proposal for altimeter application.

Validation of altimeter derived ocean current estimates against *in situ* measurements

The validation exercise was based on correlation analyses between altimeter cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies and similar anomalies deduced from four current meter moorings crossing the Norwegian Atlantic Current with meters covering the whole water column. Albeit the mismatch between the Topex/Poseidon track and the current meter cross-section, several interesting results were revealed. Firstly, the correlation showed significantly higher values for altimeter data points over the same depth contours as the current meters. This supports the hypothesis that the currents in this region are steered by the topography.

The specific correlation coefficients between the altimeter geostrophic velocities and the cross track velocity component from the current meters were not particularly high. The highest correlation was found to be 0.65 between measured currents in the 300 m level and the altimeter track point at the same depth contour. This result was expected in view of the distance between the moorings and the altimeter pass, the spatial averaging over several kilometres and the fact that the altimeter measurement is based on the geostrophic approximation, while the current meter measures the total current. In general, similar correlation between measurements and simulated results from ocean current models are not particularly higher.

It is difficult to see that sea surface anomaly derived ocean currents can represent more than quantitative or descriptive results, because it is unlikely that derived values can reach the same accuracy as measured data even after extensive comparisons with *in situ* measurements. This is because the EKE values at best represents a barotropic or geostrophic signal.

Development of altimeter data products

Several altimeter data products have been developed to meet the needs of the pre-operational system, allowing for efficiently processing of both archived HH altimeter data and new NRT altimeter data. In view of evaluating the oceanography of the study area, the regional maps of the eddy kinetic energy and Reynolds stresses have been much useful. These maps show spatial and temporal variability of the region and the interpretation of these maps have been important for throwing light upon the seasonal variability of the Norwegian Atlantic Current. At specific locations, pockets of higher EKE are found in areas where measurements and model results show the same tendency. This was expected because mesoscale activity is generally higher in vicinity of strong currents. A comparison between the conditions in the Faeroe – Shetland Channel and along the continental slope further to the north supports the general picture of the currents in the region. Even the second branch of Atlantic water following the deep slope of the Voering Plateau can be identified in the maps of the Reynolds stresses.

To utilise the repeat cycle of Topex/Poseidon, maps showing ten-day averages of sea level anomalies and the geostrophic velocity vector have been presented. These maps, representing an attempt to show the short-term variability, have not been possible to validate against

measurements or model results. The results look convincing but the ten-day repeat can be too long to resolve the dynamics of eddies in the area. A proper validation should be performed when reliable model results are available.

Assess the benefits and cost-effectiveness of near real time as well as delayed altimeter data products

The main benefit of altimeter data is that they can provide 10-day synoptic current maps, and maps which are averaged over longer time periods (months – year). Other observations techniques can only observe currents in selected points and cannot provide coverage over larger ocean areas. The cost-effectiveness of altimeter data is very good because the main cost is due to data processing. Near real time and time delayed data can become very interesting for monitoring because there are few other systems which can provide ocean current data in this mode. Oil companies can use near real time data for example in monitoring upstream current to detect eddies and features which represent maximum current speeds.

5. Exploitation (WP 5000)

5.1 Cost-benefit assessment (WP 5100)

The perceptions of oceanographic information and data acquisition will still be that *in situ* measurements constitute the backbone. Remotely sensed data and simulated data from numerical models are and will be playing an even more important role in providing data. With the development of refined microwave radar techniques and new data products it is now possible to observe and quantify several oceanographic processes and phenomena such as fronts, eddies and current features.

The altimeter data products shown in this project have addressed the spatial and temporal variability of processes associated with geostrophic currents. The present results and results obtained in NDP have confirmed to the full extent that the variability is substantial overstated compared to the general understanding prior to the project start. This is evident for seasonal variability as well as annual variability.

To perform *in situ* measurements is expensive and in hindsight, it would have been impossible to cover the annual variations with direct measurements. A dense net of *in situ* measurements is very expensive and combined with long-term measurements it is evidently constraining. In this sense the information provided by the altimeter data has had the effect that estimates based on short measurement periods had grossly underestimated the extreme currents and the consequence of this would have been alarming.

The cost effectiveness of applying sea surface anomalies derived from altimeter data can be linked to the following items:

- Altimeter data will give a descriptive picture of the mesoscale activity over a region and, assuming that the variability over the region is relatively equal, this gives a useful indication of the expected activities in the requested area.
- Initial analysis and mapping can be used to decide where to perform representative *in situ* measurements and thereby reduce the risk of making non-representative measurements and later wrong interpretation of the results.
- In combination with short-term current measurements (≈ 2 months), the altimeter data can indicate if the selected period is typical, if it is likely that extremes are recorded. This reduces the uncertainty about seasonal and annual variability.

5.2 Dissemination (WP 5200)

5.2.1 Presentation of results

A project web site (<http://www.nrsc.no/Operalt>) has been established to provide overview of results, meetings and publications. The web site presents the project objectives, study area, major results and the consortium. A two-page colour flier has been prepared giving a brief summary of the project and its results (see Appendix). This was handed out at an EU information meeting in Brussels on 6 October 1999 and at other conferences. Technical papers have been produced for publication to provide background for potential customers.

Presentation of results at conferences:

1. CEO Workshop on Marine and Coastal Remote Sensing in Lisbon, 1 –2 July 1998
2. Metocean Workshop of the Norwegian Deepwater Programme in Oslo, 2 December 1998
3. SAR Coastal and Marine Workshop at John Hopkins University, USA, 23 – 25 March 1999
4. IGARSS'99 at a session on ocean currents and fronts in Hamburg 28 June – 2 July 1999
5. CEOS SAR Workshop in Toulouse, France, 26 – 29 October 1999 (paper published in Proceedings)
6. Final Metocean Workshop of the NDP in Stavanger 13-14 March 2000.
7. ISOPE 2000 Offshore and Polar Engineering Conference, Seattle, USA, 28 May - 2 June 2000 (paper published in Proceedings)

8. EurOCEAN 2000. The European Conference on Marine Science and Ocean Technology, Hamburg, Germany, 29 August – 2 September 2000.

5.2.2 Data products available

The historical homogeneous (HH) data are available from 20/11/1998 to 9/5/1999 for the OPERALT area of study. Data are located on the anonymous ftp site: ftp.cls.fr

cd pub/oceano/OPERALT/

SLA/ along track sea level anomalies in millimetre

GVEL/ across track geostrophic velocities in millimetre/second.

MSLA/ mapped sea level anomalies from T/P and ERS-2 combined in millimetre

MGVEL/ mapped geostrophic velocities millimetre/second and associated mapping errors in percent of the signal variance, derived from the MSLA

NRT data are available from 9/5/1999 to present:

cd pub/oceano/OPERALT/NRT/ (for subdirectories, see the above tree structure)

5.2.3 Potential customers and plans for further exploitation of the results

In addition to Norske Shell, the whole consortium of eight oil companies working off Mid Norway are potential customers of the results from OPERALT. The results were presented to these companies at the Workshop in Stavanger 13 - 14 March 2000. Another consortium working in the Faroe Island – Shetland area have also expressed interest in the results. Furthermore, Norske Shell will present the results to Shell International and other companies which operate world-wide in the deep water areas.

NERSC in cooperation with CLS and Norske Shell plan to develop the altimeter technique to observe ocean currents further through new projects where potential customers can co-fund the development and marketing work for a service which uses altimeter data in monitoring and prediction of ocean currents.

6. Conclusion and recommendation

Sea level measurements by satellite radar altimeters (RA) represent a relatively low-cost data which can be used for global mapping for ocean currents. Recent improvements in orbit determinations and geoid modeling, and the availability of overlapping coverage from two satellites ERS and Topex/Poseidon have been exploited in this project in order to estimate regional currents more accurately which is required by oil companies producing oil from floating platforms primarily in deep offshore areas.

Along track data sets and maps of sea surface elevation and geostrophic velocities were produced, adapted, using our knowledge of the dynamics, to the region of interest. Both HH and NRT data are treated, and the validity and accuracy of the NRT is checked against the more precise HH data. The accuracy of the NRT is about 2 cm RMS for the T/P and ERS-2 combined maps, and the accuracy is better for along track data since there are less errors generated by time windows, and the statistics are performed on the same amount of data since only co-located HH and NRT data enter in the calculations of the statistics. HH data offer a good set of data over an extended period of time (6 year), and NRT data, even if less precise, give altimetric measurements with a roughly 2 cm RMS precision and a short time delay (2 days to a week).

The benefits and cost-effectiveness of the NRT and off-line altimeter data products have been positively assessed by A/S Norske Shell. Tools for altimeter analysis and presentation have been developed to meet the needs of a pre-operational system capable of efficiently processing archived and new NRT altimeter data, but further improvements of these tools are needed to make them more user-friendly. Several innovative altimeter data products have been developed in consultation with A/S Norske Shell who is a user of the products off the coast of Norway. Example of products shown in this report include maps of root mean square sea level variability and eddy kinetic energy, plots of sea level and cross track velocities for selected track segments, time series plots at selected locations, gridded sea level and velocity fields and spatial and temporal statistics. All these products should be developed further and be verified by comparison with other methods.

A first validation of the altimeter products against the in situ data have been done using current mooring measurements. In addition, error estimates and information on the spatio-temporal scales of variability have been studied. More validation work will be needed in order to establish quantitatively the current data from altimeter, and to interpret the data which represent a new approach to understand the circulation on regional and local scale.

The possibility to use near real time current estimates in operational monitoring of currents should be further explored. Such monitoring could be an important part of an operational service where propagation of anomalies with the mean current, such as eddies, can be predicted. The combination of altimeter derived currents and high-resolution ocean current models is also an interesting approach to improve operational oceanography.

The assessment of advantages and disadvantages of the different products can be summarized as follows:

Advantages

- The altimeter data from existing satellites represent a unique source of information from all ocean areas, providing relatively long time series (≈ 10 years) and good spatial resolution to capture the large current systems
- A combination of altimeter data from Topex/Poseidon with relatively high temporal sampling (10 day repeat cycle) and ERS with relatively high spatial sampling can provide a descriptive picture of the mesoscale current activity over a region and this gives a useful indication of the eddy kinetic energy in the requested area.
- The initial analysis and mapping can be used to decide where to perform representative *in situ* measurements and thereby reduce the risk of making non-representative measurements and later wrong interpretation of the results.
- In combination with short-term current measurements (≈ 2 months), the altimeter data can indicate if the selected period is typical, if it is likely that extremes are recorded. This reduces the uncertainty about seasonal and annual variability.
- New altimeter missions are planned in the future (Geosat Follow-on, Jason-1 and ENVISAT) which will secure continuous access to altimeter data
- Better estimation of the marine geoid (through the ESA GOCE mission) will enable estimation of absolute dynamic topography which can be translated into geostrophic currents. This will be a significant improvement in the data processing, avoiding the indirect approach by using the SLA.

Disadvantages

- Time and spatial variability for mesoscale eddies cannot be resolved properly with existing altimeter systems.
- It is difficult to see that sea surface anomaly derived ocean currents can represent more than quantitative or descriptive results, and it is unlikely that derived values can reach the same accuracy as measured data even after extensive comparisons with *in situ* measurements. This is because the EKE values at best represents a barotropic or geostrophic signal.
- The technique is relatively new and not yet accepted by the oceanographical community as a reliable method similar to traditional measurement systems. More validation and verification studies are therefore needed.

ing of altimeter data, including all the corrections, is complicated which access to high quality current information difficult for the time being. He the user access to altimeter data and derived products such as current estimates is improving constantly.

7. Acknowledgement

The development and validation of altimeter data products have been supported by the European Commission through the OPERALT project (Contract no. ENV4-CT98-0739), Norske Shell a.s. and the Norwegian Research Council.

8. References

- AVISO User Handbook : Merged TOPEX/POSEIDON Products, 1994. AVI-NT-02-101-C, Edition second, Address: AVISO/CNES, Toulouse, France. <http://www-aviso.cls.cnes.fr>
- Bentsen, M., G. Evensen, H. Drange, A.D. Jenkins, 1999. Coordinate transformation on a sphere using conformal mapping. Monthly Weather Review, in press.
- Bleck R., C. Rooth, D. Hu, L.T. Smith, 1992. Salinity-driven thermocline transients in a wind- and thermohaline-forced isopycnic coordinate model of the North Atlantic. Journal of Physical Oceanography, volume 24, pp. 1486-1505.
- Eanes, J. G. and S.V Bettadpur., 1995. The CSR 3.0 Global Ocean Tide Model. CSR-TM-95-06, Center for Space research University of Texas, Austin.
- Evensen, Geir, et al., 1999. DIADEM, ongoing project on ocean modeling and data assimilation funded under EU MAST 3.
- Gaspar, P., P.Y. le Traon and O.Z. Zanife, 1994: Estimating the sea state bias of the TOPEX and POSEIDON altimeters from crossover differences. J. Geophys. Res., 99, 24981-24994.
- Hansen, B., S.A. Malmberg, O.H. Saalen, and S. Osterhus 1986. Measurements of the flow north of the Faroe Islands June 1986. ICES C.M. C:12, 12 pp.
- Haugen, V.E.J, P. Samuel, S. Sandven, O.M. Johannessen. Norwegian Deep Water Programme Metocean Project. Ocean current investigation on the continental slope using satellite altimeter data. Final Report. NERSC Tech. Rep. No. 140. 1998
- Johannessen, O. M., S. Sandven, H. Espedal and B. Furevik. SAR research and application activities for coastal management in Norwegian waters. Proceedings of CEOS SAR Workshop 26 – 29 October 1999, Toulouse, France. (In press).
- Le Traon, P.Y., P. Gaspar, F. Bouyssel and H. Makhmaraa, 1995: Use of TOPEX/POSEIDON data to enhance ERS-1 data, J. Atm. Ocean. Tech., 12, 161-170.

- Le Traon, P.Y., P. Gaspar, F. Ogor, and J. Dorandeu, 1995: Satellites work in tandem to improve accuracy of data, EOS, Trans. AGU, 76, 385,389.
- Le Traon, P.Y., and F. Ogor, 1997: ERS-1/2 orbit improvement using TOPEX/POSEIDON: the 2 centimeter challenge, J. Geophys. Res.
- Skagseth, Ø, K. A. Orvik and M. Mork, Long-term current measurements in the Svinøy Section. Data report series, 1995 - 1997. Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen.
- Sandven, S., K. Kloster and T. Hamre. Satellite Remote Sensing of Ocean Conditions - Fronts and Eddies. Metocean Project, Norwegian Deepwater Programme, c/o A/S Norske Shell. NERSC Technical Report no. 161, November 1998, 68 pp.
- Skagseth, Ø, K. A. Orvik and M. Mork, Long-term current measurements in the Svinøy Section. Data report series, 1995 - 1997. Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen.
- Witter, D.L, D.B. Chelton, 1991, "A geosat altimeter wind speed algorithm development", J. of Geophys. Res. (oceans), 96, 8853-8860, 1991.
- Witter, D.L, D.B. Chelton, 1991: A geosat altimeter wind speed algorithm development, J. of Geophys. Res. (oceans), 96, 8853-8860.

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A1: Management plan and Quality Assurance

Project management plan

The project has been managed according to the WP structure shown in Fig. I, the Pertt diagram in Fig. II and the time schedule shown in Fig. III.

Figure I. Organisation of the project work packages

Pert diagram

Figure II. The links between the work packages

Project schedule

Figure III. Time schedule of workpackages, reports and meetings

Quality Assurance Plan

To ensure high quality of the work and results in this project the procedures described below were used.

- establish a good project plan with a list of activities to be carried out and their time schedule,
- make a realistic cost estimate for the project according to the amount of work expected in the activities to be carried out
- foresee problems that may arise in the project and take these into accounts at an early stage,
- control the work progress and accumulated costs during the project,
- follow the time schedule or revise it if necessary to complete all work within the project period
- facilitate review of project status by external reviewers at any time,
- present well-structured, clear and understandable deliverables,
- make sure that the awarding authority is satisfied with the results and deliverables.
- selection of qualified and experienced personnel for the project,
- reports from the project are reviewed by a senior scientist not involved in the project work,
- all material and documents in the project are treated confidential prior to their release.

A2: Ten days current maps combined with SAR images

Case 1: 19 June 1997

The ERS-2 SAR image which was acquired at 21:32 Z on June 19th near the Ormen Lange field, is shown in Figure A1. The left part of the image is dominated by a uniform area without clear structures at the surface. In the right part, the presence of slicks makes it possible to identify a cyclonic eddy which is 20-30 km in diameter. A few smaller eddies are also seen in the lower right part of the image. There was a T/P altimeter track over the image area three days earlier (16 June).

The sea level anomalies and the cross-track geostrophic current from the 16 June track are superimposed on the SAR image. Also the averaged geostrophic velocity vector field based on all tracks over the 10-day period from the 13 to the 23 June is superimposed on the image.

This is one example where there is reasonable good consistency between current features in the SAR image and calculated currents from the altimeter data. The current field from the altimeter data shows a cyclonic eddy near the center of the image, while the eddy in the SAR image is displaced some 30 km to the northeast, which can be interpreted as a propagation of the eddy. The current components from the single altimeter track also shows that there is a cyclonic circulation with minimum velocity in the center of the eddy. The fact that the eddy shows up clearly in the 10-day averaged velocity field suggests that the eddy has been fairly stationary sitting in the same area for several days.

Figure A1: ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 19.06.97 overlaid with altimeter along-track anomalies (coloured dots), and cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies (green arrows) on 16.06.97 and mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies (red arrows) for the period 13.06.97 to 23.06.97

Case 2: 16 July 1997

The ERS-2 SAR image acquired on July 16, 1997 near the Helland-Hansen – Ormen-Lange area is shown in Figure A2. It shows two cyclonic eddies, made visible by the presence of slicks. The Topex/Poseidon altimeter Track 118 crosses the location of the lower eddy two days later on 18.07.97, but seems to indicate an anticyclonic circulation there. The mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies for the period 13.07.97 to 23.07.97 also show an anticyclonic circulation in this area. At the location of the northernmost eddy, a cyclonic circulation is indicated, although it is difficult to see whether it is an eddy or just a meander.

Figure A2: ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 16.07.97 overlaid with altimeter along-track anomalies (coloured dots), and cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies (green arrows) on 18.07.97 and mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies (red arrows) for the period 13.07.97 to 23.07.97.

Case 3: 19 July 1997

The ERS-2 SAR image acquired on July 19th, 1997 is shown in Figure A3. It overlaps the image described in the previous section and it appears as though the two cyclonic eddies observed then have propagated northeastwards. The Topex/Poseidon altimeter Track 139 crosses in the vicinity of the southernmost eddy about 4 hours after the SAR acquisition time, and shows negative sea level anomalies and a cyclonic velocity anomaly structure. The mapped velocity anomalies for the period 13.07.97 to 23.07.97 also show a cyclonic circulation at the location of this eddy. However, further north, the circulation patterns do not agree with the SAR image. It has to be remembered that the mapped anomalies represent an average over 10 days, and in a situation where there is significant eddy propagation during this period, one would not expect to find close correspondence with an instantaneous SAR image.

Figure A3: ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 19.07.97 overlaid with altimeter along-track anomalies (coloured dots), and cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies (green arrows) on 19.07.97 and mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies (red arrows) for the period 13.07.97 to 23.07.97.

A3: Statistics on the Sea Level Anomalies

Figure A4: Mean T/P SLA of NRT-HH from 7 April to 6 July 1999. (Mean of the map: 1.3cm).

Figure A5: Mean ERS-2 SLA of NRT-HH from 7 April to 6 July 1999. (Mean of the map 2.9cm).

Figure A6: Mean T/P and ERS-2 SLA of NRT-HH from 7 April to 6 July 1999. (Mean of the map: 1.8cm).

Figure A7: RMS of T/P SLA of NRT-HH from 7 April to 6 July 1999. (Mean of the map: 2.5cm).

Figure A8: RMS of ERS-2 SLA of NRT-HH from 7 April to 6 July 1999. (Mean of the map: 4.7cm).

Figure A9: RMS of T/P and ERS-2 SLA of NRT-HH from 7 April to 6 July 1999. (Mean of the map: 1.8cm)

Figure A10: T/P NRT-HH EKE from 7 April to 6 July 1999. (Mean of the map: 12.3cm²/sec²).

Figure A11: ERS-2 NRT-HH EKE from 7 April to 6 July 1999. (Mean of the map: 45.3cm²/sec²).

Figure A12: T/P and ERS-2 NRT-HH EKE from 7 April to 6 July 1999. (Mean of the map: 28.0cm²/sec²).

Figure A13. Statistics for ERS-1/CERSAT-2 and T/P. top: mean SLA, centre: standard deviation, bottom: Eddy kinetic energy.

Figure A14. Statistics for ERS-2/CERSAT-2 and T/P data. top: mean SLA, centre: standard deviation of the SLA, bottom: Eddy kinetic energy.

Figure A15. Seasonal Eddy Kinetic Energy for January to March of 1993 to 1998.

Figure A16. Seasonal eddy kinetic energy for April to June of 1993 to 1998.

Figure A17. Seasonal eddy kinetic energy for July to September of 1993 to 1998.

Figure A18. Seasonal eddy kinetic energy for July to September of 1993 to 1997.

Figure A 19. Seasonal mean of mapped sea level anomaly for January to March of 1993 to 1998.

Figure A20. Seasonal mean of mapped sea level anomaly for April to June of 1993 to 1998.

Figure A21. Seasonal mean of mapped sea level anomaly for July to September of 1993 to 1998.

Figure A22. Seasonal mean of mapped sea level anomaly for October to December of 1993 to 1998.

A4: Time series from current moorings and cross-track altimeter data

Figure A23 Time series of cross-track current anomalies from the current meter mooring S1 (depths 100, 300 & 480 m) and altimeter data points 6-8 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42.

Figure A24. Time series of cross-track current anomalies from the current meter mooring S2 (depths 100, & 300 m) and altimeter data points 7-9 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42.

Figure A25: Time series of cross-track current anomalies from the current meter mooring E1 (depths 100, & 300 m) and altimeter data points 9-11 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42.

Figure A26: Time series of cross-track current anomalies from the current meter mooring E2 (depths 100, & 300 m) and altimeter data points 11-13 along Topex/Poseidon Track 42.

A5. The project flier

OPERALT

Operational Altimetry for the Offshore Oil Industry

(European Commission DGXII-D Contract No. ENV4-CT98-0739)

Overall objective:

To develop a pre-operational altimeter data analysis and archival system for ocean currents, and to assess the benefits and cost-effectiveness of the ocean current information provided by such a system for applications by the major customer group: the offshore oil industry, both on a regional and the global scale.

Specific objectives:

- produce accurate high-resolution local altimetric mean sea level for the study area
- produce merged ERS-1/2 and T/P data sets for the study area
- validate altimeter-derived current estimates against *in situ* measurements
- analyze user requirements and develop appropriate altimeter data products
- cost-benefit analysis

Customer background:

The project consortium includes Norske Shell A/S as a partner. Together with 5 other offshore oil companies, Shell has an ongoing programme for monitoring metocean conditions in seven licensing areas off midwest Norway, which includes a section of the continental slope. As oil exploration and production activities move from the continental shelf to deeper waters, information on the ocean current field becomes increasingly important. Satellite altimetry can provide important inputs in this context, and this project is an attempt at maximising the benefits of altimeter data for offshore oil exploration, production and support activities.

Study area:

We focus on an area where a comprehensive monitoring programme, including field measurements, satellite remote sensing and numerical modelling, was initiated by a consortium of offshore oil companies led by Norske Shell A/S. The figure shows the bathymetry in the area, overlaid with ERS-2 and Topex/Poseidon altimeter tracks and positions of the 4 current meter moorings (V) used in the validation study. At the continental slope (red/green), the depth rapidly increases from the <200 m (yellow) of the shelf to the >1000 m of the deep ocean (blue).

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OPERALT

Results:

A customer requirements analysis has been prepared. This can be viewed at the project web site, <http://www.nrsc.no/Operalt>

Estimates of precise mean sea surface has been produced from ERS-1/2 and Topex/Poseidon data.

ERS-2 and Topex/Poseidon data have been merged to produce a continuous, 7 year data set gridded at approximately 10 km and 10 day intervals.

Altimeter data products, such as plots of the distribution of root mean square of sea level anomalies, eddy kinetic energy (Top figure shows EKE distribution averaged over Jan-Mar, 1993-'98. Red and yellow represent high energy areas along the path of the Atlantic inflow, with EKE over $100 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-2}$) and Reynolds stress, time series of sea level anomalies and velocity anomalies, maps of altimeter velocity anomalies overlaid on SAR imagery (Middle figure shows an ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 27.09.97, overlaid with sea level anomalies - coloured dots, in cm - cross-track velocity anomalies - green arrows - and mapped geostrophic velocities - red arrows - from altimetry.), etc. have been produced.

Altimeter-derived cross track velocity anomalies have been validated against field measurements by current meter moorings. Cross-track velocity anomalies from altimetry had correlation co-efficients up to 0.65 against similar observations from the current meter moorings. (Bottom figure shows the current meter measurements from mooring S1 at 100, 300 and 480 m depths - coloured solid lines - and altimeter data which showed best correlation - o, x, +)

